

A CRITICAL ANALYSIS OF DISINVESTMENT IN
BHARAT PETROLEUM CORPORATION LIMITED
FUTURE FINANCIAL PERFORMANCE
AND
IMPACT ON INDIAN ECONOMY

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Abstract

On November 20, 2019 Cabinet Committee on Economic Affairs (CCEA) chaired by the Prime Minister Shri Narendra Modi approved disinvestment in 5 Central Public Sector Enterprises (CPSEs) including Bharat Petroleum Corporation Limited (BPCL)- a profitable government company. The decision of selling all the government stock in BPCL through strategic sale has brought on many criticism as the benefited stated by the government of disinvestment is lesser than its benefits to Indian economy if the stock is retained by the government. To check whether these criticisms are true that BPCL is performing well and contributing more if it is under the government ownership, I compared the future financial performance of BPCL if it is privatised with the future financial performance if it is not privatised. I used liner regression model with intercept and liner regression model without intercept to estimate the future financial performance under the both of the case. To check the argument of the bad impact of the decision on Indian economy I estimated the fiscal deficit under both the cases using weighted average mean taking the base of estimations presented in the Union Budget 2020-21. To analyse, whether the method of the disinvestment- strategic sale- is better or the alternate method- Share Issue Privatisation (SIP)- I compared both the methods conceptually with support of empirical data. The results shows that BPCL will perform well under the government ownership in the terms of profitability and efficiency. BPCL can perform well under the ownership of private ownership only if it rises its product price or by reducing the work force size. The fiscal deficit is lower for the fiscal year 2020-21 if BPCL is privatised, but this benefits is only of the short term in the nature. The government has to give up the dividend revenue from BPCL if it is privatised which will effect negatively to more than one fiscal years. Empirical data shows government can generate more disinvestment revenue through the SIP but its process is more time consuming. The other reason why government should choose SIP method is that it will help Indian capital market on the other hand strategic sale method will is beneficial to only

one entity- the buyer (and in the situation of 'Winner Curse' it will not benefit the buyer too). In my opinion, rather than privatising BPCL- a profitable CPSE- government should privatise any other loss making CPSE to unblock the resources, divert them to productive activities and increase the efficiency in the loss making CPSE by handing over them to the private owners.

Key Words: Bharat Petroleum Corporation Limited, Central Public Sector Enterprise, Disinvestment, Privatisation, Strategic Sale, Indian Economy, Financial Analysis

Declaration

I, do hereby declare that the material embodied in the present work entitled 'A Critical Analysis of Disinvestment in Bharat Petroleum Corporation Limited' submitted to The Maharaja Sayajirao University of Baroda in partial fulfilment for the award of the degree of Bachelors of Business Administration is a record of original and independent research work done by me under the supervision and guidance of Mr. Justin John, Department of Business Economics, Faculty of Commerce, The Maharaja Sayajirao University of Baroda. This research work has not previously formed the basis for the award of any Degree, Diploma, Associateship, fellowship or any other similar titles. My indebtedness to other works has been duly acknowledged at the relevant places.

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Certificate

This is to certify that the thesis titled 'A Critical Analysis of Disinvestment in Bharat Petroleum Corporation Limited' is being submitted by Mr. Shiv Mukeshbhai Katira for the award of degree of Bachelors of Business Administration from The Maharaja Sayajirao University of Baroda. It is further to certify that this research work has been carried out under my supervision and no part of it has been submitted elsewhere for any degree and diploma. It is worthy of consideration for evaluation and acceptance. The assistance and help received during the course of this work and sources of information have been duly acknowledged.

Mr. Justin John
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Place: Vadodara, Gujarat, India

Date:

Preface

Indian Economy- one of the largest and fastest growing economies in the world- facing many problems after the decision of demonetisation and implementation of new indirect tax system- Goods and Services Tax (GST). The government tried many corrective steps to boost our economy. Many steps have been taken to minimise fiscal deficit and minimising debt of the government.

Recently, the Government of India (GoI) announced disinvestment in 5 Central Public Sector Enterprises (CPSEs) expecting total receipt of ₹1.05 lakh crore. Bharat Petroleum Corporation Limited (BPCL) is one these CPSEs. Though BPCL is performing well and yielding good returns to the government, the decision of privatising this CPSE has brought on a lot of criticism. Many economists and authours argued that the outlook of the government is short term in nature. Some of them stated that it shows pessimism of the government to privatise profitable government company when it is profitable.

As the part of the third year Bachelors of Business Administration (BBA) Programme, I chose the topic ‘A Critical Analysis of Disinvestment in Bharat Petroleum Corporation Limited: Future Financial Performance and Impact on Indian Economy’ for the paper ‘Project and Viva Voce’. In this research work I critically examined the decision of the government to privatise BPCL from the point of view of its future financial performance and its impact on Indian economy.

This research work is carried out during the nation-wide lock-down because of coronavirus (COVID-19) pandemic. I utilised this time to make the project more in-depth. I used Microsoft Excel for statistical calculations. Unlike other under-graduation students, I used \LaTeX for making this project and not the Microsoft Word. I made this project on <https://www.overleaf.com> an online platform to make documents using \LaTeX .

I would like to thank my project guide, Mr. Justin John who made this proposition possible in every way and whose guiding hand was invaluable in helping me complete the final stage of the under-graduation programme. I am deeply indebted to all the teaching and non-teaching staff of the BBA Programme, Faculty of Commerce, The Maharaja Sayajirao University of Baroda who always helped me whenever I needed. I am grateful to the Smt. Hansa Mehta Library and the Computer Centre of The Maharaja Sayajirao University of Baroda for providing me resources without which this research work was impossible. I am also grateful to my family members who shored up my spirits and gave moral support throughout the research work.

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Abbreviations

AIF	Alternative Investment Fund
BGRL	Bharat Gas Resources Limited
BHEL	Bharat Heavy Electricals Limited
BPCL	Bharat Petroleum Corporation Limited
BPRL	Bharat Petro Resources Limited
BRL	Bharat Refineries Limited
BSE	Bombay Stock Exchange
BSM	Burmah Shell Oil Storage & Distributing Company of India Limited
BSR	Burmah-Shell Refineries Limited
CAPM	capital Asset Pricing Model
CCEA	Cabinet Committee on Economic Affairs
CGD	Core Group of Disinvestment
CONCOR	Container Corporation of India Limited
COVID-19	Coronavirus Disease 2019
CPSE	Central Public Sector Enterprise
CSB	Confirmed Selected Bidder
CU	Confidentiality Undertaking
DCF	Discounted Cash Flow
DIPAM	Department of Investment and Public Asset Management
DR	Data Room
DTTILLP	Deloitte Touche Tohmatsu India LLP
EBITDA	Earnings before Interest, Taxes, Depreciation & Amortisations
EoI	Expression of Interest
ESOP	Employee Stock Ownership Plan
ETF	Exchange Traded Fund

EV	Enterprise Value
FCF	free cash flows
FD	Fiscal Deficit
FPO	Further Public Offering
GDP	Gross Domestic Product
GOI	Government of India
GST	Goods and Services Tax
IBP	Indo Bright Petroleum
IOC	Indian Oil Corporation
IP	Interested Parties
IPO	Initial Public Offering
ITDC	Indian Tourism Development Corporation
LLP	Limited Liability Partnership
MFIL	Modern Food Industries Limited
MMT	Million Metric Tonne
MMTC	Minerals & Metals Trading Corporation Limited
NAV	Net Asset Value
NDCR	Non-debt Capital Receipts
NMDC	National Mineral Development Corporation
NRL	Numaligarh Refinery Limited
NSE	National Stock Exchange
OMC	Oil Marketing Company
PAT	Profit After Tax
PBDIT	Profit Before Depreciation, Interest and Tax
PBIT	Profit Before Interest and Tax
PBT	Profit Before Tax
PIB	Press Information Bureau
PIM	Preliminary Information Memorandum
PSU	Public Sector Undertaking
QIP	Qualified Interested Parties
RBI	Reserve Bank of India
RFP	Request for Proposal

RIL	Reliance Industries Limited
SBU	Strategic Business Unit
SCI	Shipping Corporation of India
SEBI	Securities and Exchange Board of India
SIP	Share Issue Privatisation
SOE	State Owned Enterprise
SPA	Share Purchase Agreement
TA	Transaction Advisor
USD	United States Dollar
WACC	Weighted Average Cost of Capital

Chapter 1

Introduction

1.1 Disinvestment: A Theoretical Overview

1.1.1 What is Disinvestment?

The term 'Disinvestment' means selling the investments (generally fixed assets). The term is 'Disinvestment' is generally used when government sells its assets in the State Owned Enterprises (SOEs) (See Definition 2 State Owned Enterprises and Definition 5 Disinvestment for more clarification).

Most of the time 'Disinvestment' and 'Privatisation' (See Definition 4 Privatisation) are considered as the synonymous of each other; but they are different. When government sells some of its investment in SOE and retaining the other part under its ownership it is known as 'Disinvestment'; on the other hand when government sells all the assets of the SOE with the control and management to any private owner then it is known as 'Privatisation'.

We will study basic theoretic concepts about the disinvestment and the privatisation in this following subsections.

1.1.2 Different Approaches for Disinvestment¹

1.1.2.1 Minority Disinvestment

A minority disinvestment is one such that, at the end of it, the government retains a majority stake in the company, typically greater than 51%, thus ensuring management control. Historically, minority stakes have been either auctioned off to institutions (financial) or offloaded to the public by way of an Offer for Sale.

1.1.2.2 Majority Disinvestment

A majority disinvestment is one in which the government, post disinvestment, retains a minority stake in the company i.e. it sells off a majority stake. Historically, majority disinvestments have been typically made to strategic partners. These partners could be other Central Public Sector Enterprises (CPSEs) themselves or these can be private entities. The stake can also be offloaded by way of an Offer for Sale, separately or in conjunction with a sale to a strategic partner.

1.1.2.3 Complete Privatisation

Complete privatisation is a form of majority disinvestment wherein 100% control of the company is passed on to a buyer. Disinvestment and privatisation are often loosely used interchangeably. There is, however, a vital difference between the two. Disinvestment may or may not result in Privatisation. When the Government retains 26% of the shares carrying voting powers while selling the remaining to a strategic buyer, it would have disinvested, but would not have 'privatised', because with 26%, it can still stall vital decisions for which generally a special resolution (three-fourths majority) is required (See definition 4 Privatisation and definition 5 Disinvestment.)

1.1.3 Methods of Disinvestment¹

1.1.3.1 Strategic Sale to Private Entity

Transactions involving sales made by the Government of CPSEs, including subsidiary of CPSEs, along with transfer of management control, to a strategic private partner identified

¹This information is retrieved from BSE PSU website

through a process of competitive bidding and subsequent sales to the partner through call/put options is known as ‘Strategic Sale to Private Entity’. (See Subsection 1.1.4 Strategic Sale.)

1.1.3.2 Public Offer

Transactions involving sales made by the Government in CPSEs through a Public Offer is known as ‘Public Offer’. It is also known as Share Issue Privatisation (SIP) (For more clarification see definition 7 Share Issue Privatisation).

1.1.3.3 CPSE to CPSE Sale

Transactions involving sales made by the Government of one CPSE to another CPSE is known as ‘CPSE to CPSE Sale’.

1.1.3.4 Auction to Financial Investors

Transactions involving sales made by the Government in CPSEs through an auction to defined financial investors/investor groups (like public sector financial institutions) is known as ‘Auction to Financial Investors’.

1.1.3.5 Auction to Private Entity

Transactions involving sales made by the Government in CPSEs through an auction to private entities is known as ‘Auction to Private Entity’.

1.1.3.6 Sale To Employees

Transactions involving sales made by the Government to employees of the respective CPSEs is known as ‘Sale To Employees’.

1.1.3.7 Institutional Placement Programme

Transactions involving sales made by the Government through Institutional Placement Programme in CPSEs is known as ‘Institutional Placement Programme’.

1.1.3.8 Buyback

Transactions involving buyback of Shares by the Company from the Government is known as 'Buyback'.

1.1.3.9 Block Deals/Market Sales

Transactions involving sales made by the Government through Block Deal or Open Market is known as 'Block Deals/Market Sales'.

1.1.3.10 Exchange Traded Fund

Transactions involving sales made by the Government through Exchange Traded Fund is known as 'Exchange Traded Fund'.

1.1.4 Strategic Sales²

In the strategic sale of a company, the transaction has two elements:

1. Transfer of a block of shares to a Strategic Partner and
2. Transfer of management control to the Strategic Partner

The transfer of shares by Government may not necessarily be such that more than 51% of the total equity goes to the Strategic Partner for the transfer of management to take place. In the case of PSUs, in order that the company no longer has the character of a Government company, the transfer of shares involves bringing down Governments shareholding below 51%. In fact, it must be remembered that Companies Act, 1956 only defines a 'Government Company' (See Definition 1 Public Sector Undertakings), which in common parlance, is a company in which Government holds more than 51%. PSU is not defined in the Act. Once the Governments shareholding goes below 51%, it ceases to be a Government company and hence, it requires changes in the Articles of Association of the company especially in relation to the Presidential directives etc. The Strategic Partner, after the transaction, may hold less percentage of shares than the Government but the control of management would be with him. For instance, if in a PSU the shareholding of Government is 51% and the balance is dispersed in public holdings,

²This section is excerpted from the document titled 'Understanding the Strategic Sale Agreement' released by Department of Investment and Public Asset Management, Ministry of Finance, Government of India

then Government may go in for a 25% strategic sale and pass on management control, though the Government would post-transfer have a larger share holding (26%) than the Strategic Partner (25%). It may be noted here that the number 26% has a special significance in Company Law as to get a special resolution passed, one requires at least $\frac{3}{4}$ majority in a general meeting. Therefore, the 26% block acts as a check. Special resolutions are required under law in case of certain critical decisions by the company such as reduction of capital, alteration in Articles of Association and Memorandum of Association, winding up of the company, issue of share with variation of rights of special classes of shareholders etc. In case of strategic sale of PSUs, Government typically has affirmative rights on several issues, which are much wider in scope than what is provided in Company Law for special resolutions. In fact, the Agreements can be structured such that these rights are exercisable even when Government holding goes below 26%. The other critical number one encounters in Company Law are 10% shareholding, below which one loses voting rights unless specially provided.

Since the shareholders mutually agree to certain rights and obligations which may by dint of the Agreement between the parties assign certain special rights and obligations on the shareholders to which they would normally not be bound through the provisions of the Company Law, the Agreements assume great significance in the case of strategic sale of PSUs. However, as mentioned earlier, in case of strategic sales, the Government has to ensure that the Agreements signed with the Strategic Partner adequately safeguard the Governments/nation's interests, the interests of the company and finally those of the employees. Therefore, these documents have to be carefully structured. This paper tries to give an insight into the issues involved, the structure of the documents, standard clauses, and the reasons behind them and how they safeguard stakeholders' interests.

1.1.4.1 Environment of the Strategic Sales

The figure 1.1 depicts the stakeholders involved in the transaction and the interface with the regulatory laws/organisations.

In a strategic sale, the obvious stakeholders are the Government and the Strategic Partner. However, there are others also whom the transaction affects. They are the other shareholders and the employees. Depending on the success of the transaction the value of the shares held by the other shareholders would behave. Therefore, they are directly affected. Transfer of shares is

Source: ‘Understanding the Strategic Sale Agreement’, Department of Investment and Public Asset Management, Ministry of Finance, Government of India

Figure 1.1: Environment for Strategic Sales

generally governed by the provisions of the Companies Act, 1956 (sections 108 etc). In case of listed companies, however, the interest of the small investors is taken care of by Securities and Exchange Board of India (SEBI) through its various regulations. What we are concerned with most are the regulations regarding takeovers, listing and de-listing. The SEBI Takeover Code gets triggered when a person acquires more than 15% of the voting equity shares of the company. Then, the person taking over these shares is required to make a public offer to purchase shares not less than 20% of the equity of the company. This provision has a great impact on the strategic sale transaction. For instance, in the example given above, the Strategic Partner would have to buy another 20% of the shares from the public which means he has to buy 45% of the shares i.e. the transaction size more than doubles, which in big PSUs may mean enormous sums of money. When the deal size goes up, it reduces the number of players and hence competition. The other impact it can have is that it reduces the floating stock, which can at times go even below 10%, resulting in de-listing of the company. Reduction in floating stock affects trading and hence impacts the value of the residual shareholding of the Government. Apart from the immediate effect the transaction would have on the share prices, the other shareholders also get

affected depending upon whether the Strategic Partner enhances corporate value and hence their earnings or not.

The employees also are equally, if not more concerned. From the security of the public sector work environment they would find themselves in a new atmosphere of increased competition, demand for higher productivity and accountability. They would, therefore, logically try not to let go the protections presently enjoyed by them. Government, in a welfare state, also would like to look after the employees' interest. There obviously has to be a trade off, however, between the protection that the employees can be given and providing to the Strategic Partner a degree of freedom to run the company. These competing interests would have to be carefully balanced in drafting the Agreements.

The PSU is clearly one important player that gets affected by the transaction. Passed on to the hands of a serious Strategic Partner, its worth goes up. But the reverse could also happen.

The Strategic Partner, perhaps, has the highest stakes. In case the deal does not work out right he loses money and reputation in the market. In case his assessment of the potential of the company, its assets/liabilities position and his ability to implement a good business plan is right, he gains money, reputation and goodwill. The questions that confront him are: Will he get effective control of the company? What kind of representations and warranties should he give? What exit options should he have? What are the safeguards against breach by Government or in case of force major events? What restrictions can he live with regarding employees etc? The Government, on the other hand, is concerned with similar questions. The Government's chief concerns would be:

1. Protection against asset stripping by the Strategic Partner.
2. Protection to employees post-disinvestment.
3. Exit options for the balance shares held by Government of India.
4. A reasonable period for which the Strategic Partner may not exit the Company ('Lock-in' period). Typically, this is $\frac{3}{5}$ years.

All these would govern the structure of the Agreements.

Typically, industries would have environmental issues, especially for manufacturing units. They may not be very relevant, however, in Consultancy Companies or Software Companies.

Therefore, the Agreements have to, at times, address the environmental issues clearly e.g. which party takes what part of the risk in regard to responsibilities for actions taken/not taken prior to disinvestment.

1.2 Disinvestment in India

1.2.1 Need for Disinvestment in India

At the time of independence, all the business activities was carried out by private sector but Jawaharlal Nehru government (1947 - 1964) gave more importance to heavy industries and established government companies for their business functioning. At the same time government reserved some industries only for government companies and regulated many industries. The main objectives for establishment of PSUs are to generate financial resources for the government; to redistribute income and wealth; to create employment opportunities; to promote export and import substitution. That is why many authors termed PSUs as engine of growth for the economy. But it should also be noted that overburdened with social obligations, most of the PSUs were failed to generate desired profit in comparison to their counterparts - private sector companies. The bias of survivor-ship is one of the reasons behind the poor performance of PSUs in comparison with private sector companies. Towards the end of 1990s, government realised that the main function of the government is to concentrate on social and physical infrastructure and not to be in the business. In 1991, P. V. Narsimha Rao government (1991 - 1996) announced many economic reforms and privatisation was one of them. As Disinvestment Commission under G. V. Ramkrishna guided that disinvestment should be for straightening PSUs and not for dismantling PSUs. The commission also advised that the receipt should not be used for government revenue expenditure as the Modi government planning to quickly sell off the assets of BPCL to bridge tax revenue short fall in economic slowdown.³

1.2.2 Evolution of Disinvestment Policy in India⁴

The liberalisation reforms undertaken in 1991 ushered in an increased demand for privatisation/ disinvestment of PSUs. In the initial phase, this was done through the sale of minority

³Some of the part in this section is excerpted from the interview of T T Ram Mohan published in 'the Hindu' on 20th December, 2019.

⁴This section is excerpted from the Economic Survey 2019-20

stake in bundles through auction. This was followed by separate sale for each company in the following years, a method popularly adopted till 1999-2000. India adopted strategic sale as a policy measure in 1999-2000 with sale of substantial portion of Government shareholding in identified CPSEs up to 50 per cent or more, along with transfer of management control. This was started with the sale of 74 per cent of the Government's equity in Modern Food Industries Limited (MFIL). Thereafter, 12 PSUs (including four subsidiaries of PSUs), and 17 hotels of Indian Tourism Development Corporation (ITDC) were sold to private investors along with transfer of management control by the Government.

In addition, 33.58 per cent shareholding of Indo Bright Petroleum (IBP) strategically sold to Indian Oil Corporation (IOC). IBP, however, remained a PSU after this strategic sale, since IOC held 53.58 per cent of its paid-up equity. Another major shift in disinvestment policy was made in 2004-05 when it was decided that the government may "dilute its equity and raise resources to meet the social needs of the people", a distinct departure from strategic sales.

Strategic Sales have got a renewed push after 2014. During 2016-17 to 2018-19, on average, strategic sales accounted for around 28.2 per cent of total proceeds from disinvestment. Department of Investment and Public Asset Management (DIPAM) has laid down comprehensive guidelines on 'Capital Restructuring of CPSEs' in May, 2016 by addressing various aspects, such as, payment of dividend, buyback of shares, issues of bonus shares and splitting of shares. The Government has been following an active policy on disinvestment in CPSEs through the various modes:

1. Disinvestment through minority stake sale in listed CPSEs to achieve minimum public shareholding norms of 25 per cent. While pursuing disinvestment of CPSEs, the Government will retain majority shareholding, i.e., at least 51 per cent and management control of the PSU ;
2. Listing of CPSEs to facilitate people's ownership and improve the efficiency of companies through accountability to its stake holders - As many as 57 PSUs are now listed with total market capitalisation of over 13 Lakh Crore.
3. Strategic Disinvestment;
4. Buy-back of shares by large PSUs having huge surplus;
5. Merger and acquisitions among PSUs in the same sector;

6. Launch of exchange traded funds (ETFs) - an equity instrument that tracks a particular index. The CPSE ETF is made up of equity investments in India's major public sector companies; and
7. Monetisation of select assets of CPSEs to improve their balance sheet/reduce their debts and to meet part of their capital expenditure requirements.

NITI Aayog has been mandated to identify PSUs for strategic disinvestment. For this purpose, NITI Aayog has classified PSUs into 'high priority' and 'low priority', based on (a) National Security (b) Sovereign functions at arm's length, and (c) Market Imperfections and Public Purpose. The PSUs falling under 'low priority' are covered for strategic disinvestment. To facilitate quick decision making, powers to decide the following have been delegated to an Alternative Mechanism in all the cases of Strategic Disinvestment of CPSEs where Cabinet Committee on Economic Affairs (CCEA) has given 'in principle' approval for strategic disinvestment:

1. The quantum of shares to be transacted, mode of sale and final pricing of the transaction or lay down the principles/ guidelines for such pricing; and the selection of strategic partner/ buyer; terms and conditions of sale; and
2. To decide on the proposals of Core Group of Disinvestment (CGD) with regard the timing, price, terms & conditions of sale, and any other related issue to the transaction.

On November 20, 2019, the government announced that full management control will be ceded to buyers of BPCL, Shipping Corporation of India (SCI) and Container Corporation of India Limited (CONCOR). On January 8, 2020, strategic disinvestment was approved for Minerals & Metals Trading Corporation Limited (MMTC), National Mineral Development Corporation (NMDC), MECON and Bharat Heavy Electricals Limited (BHEL).

1.3 Bharat Petroleum Corporation Limited

1.3.1 About the Company

Bharat Petroleum Corporation Limited (BPCL) is one of the leading integrated oil company of India and is majority owned and controlled by Government of India (GoI). The majority of the income of BPCL is derived from oil refining and marketing of petroleum products. In addition to refining and marketing business, BPCL also has interests in upstream, midstream (pipeline,

terminal, tankages) and natural gas businesses. BPCL has highly experienced management and a skilled workforce.

It is the 2nd largest oil marketing company in India with a market share of 21% in FY 19 and 3rd largest refining company in India. It is a publicly listed company.

275th on 2019's Fortune Global 500 list, BPCL is a Maharatna (See definition 3 the Maharatnas) oil and gas GoI undertaking headquartered in Mumbai, Maharashtra. BPCL is 6th largest public listed company on Fortune India's 500 largest companies by turnover in 2019 and the 2nd largest Indian Oil Marketing Company (OMC) in 2019.

With a strong success record of creating value for its customers & India over its 40+ years of existence, BPCL received the coveted Maharatna status, placing it in the category of government-owned entities in India with one of the largest market capitalisation and consistent profits, in September 2017.

BPCL operates four refineries in India, viz. Mumbai Refinery (1955), Kochi Refinery (1966), BORL-Bina Refinery (2011) and Numaligarh Refinery (1999) with a combined crude oil refining capacity of 38.3 MMTPA. The company business is divided into seven Strategic Business Units (SBUs), viz. Refinery, Retail, Lubricants, Aviation, Gas, Industrial & Commercial and LPG.

BPCL entered the upstream sector in 2003 with an aim to provide partial supply security of crude and hedging of price risks and to become a vertically integrated global oil company. A wholly-owned subsidiary company of BPCL, by the name Bharat Petro Resources Limited (BPRL) was incorporated in October 2006 and BPCL pursues its upstream business through BPRL.

BPCL incorporated Bharat Gas Resources Limited (BGRL) on 7th June 2018 as its wholly owned subsidiary for focused approach towards building its gas business. BPCL has adopted diversification in Petrochemicals as a strategy for future growth.

BPCL is engaging in value creation, enabling a digital transformation across its business units, exploring, expanding its horizons by venturing into petrochemicals, alternate fuels, battery swapping for electric vehicles, renewable energies and ultimately excelling in innovation by working closely with start-ups and encouraging its employees to innovate on the business challenges faced.

1.3.2 Ownership Structure over the Years

Burmah-Shell Refineries Limited (BSR), was incorporated on 3rd November, 1952 as a Company under the Indian Companies Act, 1913, at Mumbai, with the Authorised Capital of ₹25 Crore. A refinery was set up by this Company at Mahul, Mumbai. Secondly, the Burmah-Shell Oil Storage & Distributing Company of India Limited (BSM), a foreign Company, established in England in 1928, was carrying on in India the business of Distributing & Marketing petroleum products & for that purpose established places of business at Mumbai & other places in India.

Pursuant to the agreement dated 23rd December, 1975 between the GoI, the Burmah-Shell Oil Storage and Distributing Company of India Limited (BSM) and the Burmah Shell Refineries Limited (BSR), the GoI acquired 100 per cent equity share holding (paid up value ₹1453.83 Lakh) of BSR on 24th January, 1976, for a consideration of ₹925 Lakh. Simultaneously, through 'The Burmah Shell acquisition of Undertakings in India Act, 1976', the GoI also acquired the right, title and interest and liabilities of BSM in relation to its undertakings in India for a consideration of ₹2775 Lakh and by notification dated 24th January, 1976, vested the same in BSR) without any specific consideration payable by BSR. The name of BSR was changed to Bharat Refineries Limited (BRL) and subsequently to Bharat Petroleum Corporation Limited.

Out of the total investment of ₹3700 Lakh (₹925 Lakh + ₹2775 Lakh) made by the GoI as stated above, the Government treated an amount of ₹1128 Lakh as a repayable loan to BPCL. The net investment made by the Government thus amounted to ₹2572 Lakh (₹3700 Lakh - ₹1128 Lakh). In January 1984, the GoI made further investment of ₹203.57 Lakh in BPCL towards payment of Partly Paid Equity Shares bringing the paid up capital to ₹1657.40 Lakh (₹1453.83 Lakh + ₹203.57 Lakh).

Subsequently, during 1985-86, the reserves of BPCL to the extent of ₹1127.94 Lakh were capitalised for making Partly Paid shares as Fully Paid shares, as also to Issue bonus shares to the GoI. Thus the paid up capital was increased to ₹2785.34 Lakh without further investment by the GoI. Again in 1990, the Reserves of BPCL to the extent of ₹2214.66 Lakh were capitalised to issue Bonus Shares to the GoI and thereby increased Paid Up Capital to ₹50 Crore without further investment by the GoI.

Thus, with the investment of ₹2775.57 Lakh (i.e. ₹2572 Lakh + ₹203.57 Lakh), the GoI's holding in BPCL increased to ₹50 Crore (i.e. 5 Crore equity shares of ₹10/- each).

Out of the above, the GoI sold 1.5 Crore equity shares of ₹10/- each to Financial Institutions/Mutual Funds etc. during 1991-92 and 1992-93 and 18,99,990 equity shares to employees during 1993-94. For the above disinvestment the GoI received about ₹680 Crore. As a result of the above disinvestments the Share holdings of the GoI in the Corporation was reduced to 3,31,00,010 shares (66.20%) as on 31st March, 1994.

During 1994, BPCL declared Bonus shares in the ratio of 2:1 by way of capitalisation of reserves to the extent of ₹100 Crore. The GoI, therefore, received 6,62,00,020 Bonus Equity Shares of ₹10/- each. Accordingly, GoI's holding increased from 3,31,00,010 shares of ₹10 each to 9,93,00,030 equity shares of ₹10/- each amounting to ₹99,30,00,300/-.

During 2000-01, BPCL declared Bonus shares in the ratio of 1:1 by way of capitalisation of reserves to the extent of ₹150 Crore. The GoI, therefore, received 9,93,00,030 Bonus Equity Shares of ₹10/- each.

Accordingly, GoI's holding increased from 9,93,00,030 shares of ₹10 each to 19,86,00,060 equity shares of ₹10/- each amounting to ₹198,60,00,600/- as on 31.3.2008. Pursuant to the merger of Kochi Refineries Limited . with BPCL, vide Order dated 18th August, 2006 from Ministry of Company Affairs, the total paid up share capital of BPCL had increased to 36,15,42,124 equity shares of ₹10 each and the percentage of shareholding of the GoI has reduced from 66.20% to 54.93%.

Pursuant to disinvestment of 1,35,05,341 equity shares in FY 2017-18 and 2,19,99,057 equity shares in FY 2018-19 in favour of Bharat 22 ETF (an exchange traded fund comprising of PSU stocks) by Government of India, the holding of the President of India in the equity share capital was reduced to 52.98% as at 31st December, 2019

1.3.3 Equity Capital Structure of BPCL

BPCL has only one class of equity shares of face value of ₹10. There are no outstanding convertible instruments, including Employee Stock Ownership Plan (ESOP), which can be converted into equity. The shares of BPCL are listed on two key stock exchanges of India i.e. Bombay Stock Exchange (BSE) and National Stock Exchange (NSE). The equity share capital of the company as on 31st December, 2019 is shown in the Table 1.1.

Particulars	No. of Shares (Crore)	Equity Share Capital (₹Crore)
Authorised	263.50	2,635.00
Issued, subscribed and paid-up	216.925	2,169.25

Source: Annual Report for FY 2018-19

Table 1.1: Equity Capital Structure of BPCL

Shareholder	No. of Shares Held	% of holding
Government of India	1,14,91,83,592	52.98
Foreign Portfolio Investors	30,51,24,402	14.07
Mutual Funds / UTI	24,81,73,349	11.44
BPCL Trust for Investments in Shares	20,23,72,422	9.33
Insurance Companies	1,50,156,822	6.92
Individual Investors (Shareholding upto of ₹2 Lakh)	50,67,88,989	2.34
Bodies Corporate	2,66,61,648	1.23
Government of Kerala	1,86,66,666	0.86
Individual Investors (Shareholding in excess of ₹2 Lakh)	94,59,061	0.44
Clearing Members	36,14,699	0.17
Non Residential Indians	28,26,681	0.13
Financial Institutions / Banks	23,34,504	0.11
Total	2,16,92,52,744	100

Source: Public Disclosure Published on BPCL Website

Table 1.2: Distribution of Shareholding as on 31st December, 2019

1.3.4 BPCL Today⁵

BPCL has market share of 23.83% in the industry. It has market sales (including exports) is 44.98 Million Metric Tonne (MMT) and total revenue ₹3,40,606.13 Crore including revenue from operations ₹3,37,622.53. Its Gross profit before depreciation, interest and tax is ₹14,948 Crore and Profit after tax (PAT) is ₹7,131 Crore. Total number of man power employed in the BPCL is 11,971. Total number of retail outlets is 14,802. As on 31st December 2019, the

⁵The data shown in this section is excerpted from the BPCL Annual Report 2018-19.

market capitalisation of BPCL was ₹106,619 Crore (\$ 15 Billion). The Central Government is presently holding 1,15,60,95,962 Shares which is 52.98% of the total shares.(The table 1.2 is showing the distribution of Shareholding as on 31st December, 2019)

BPCL Trust for Investment in Shares holds 20,23,72,422 equity shares i.e. 9.33% (treasury shares) for the benefit of BPCL. It is possible that these shares may be retained, cancelled or disposed prior to the transaction; and correspondingly the total number of outstanding shares / capital structure may change. However, the number of shares to be sold in the Proposed Transaction shall remain the same.

1.4 Privatisation of BPCL

1.4.1 Decision of the Modi Government

On November 20, 2019 CCEA chaired by Prime Minister Shri Narendra Modi approved strategic disinvestment in 5 CPSEs including 52.98% stack in BPCL - one of the Maharatna PSUs stating two benefits: first - the unlocked resources will be utilised in financing social sectors/ developmental programmes which will benefit the public; second - the strategic buyer/ acquirer may bring in new management/ technology/ investment for the growth of these companies and may use innovative methods for their development.⁶ This strategic disinvestment will also generate revenue to meet targeted fiscal deficit of 3.4%⁷ of gross domestic product (GDP) for the financial year 2019-20 which is otherwise difficult to achieve amidst the economic slow-down.

1.4.2 Previous Attempts

It is not the first time that government is approving disinvestment in profitable PSUs, In February 2002, Atal Bihari Vajpayee government (1998 - 2004) also tried to privatise BPCL but the Supreme Court of India mandated parliamentary approval for the disinvestment in the oil distribution business in its judgement on September 16, 2003⁸ as the executive action for

⁶Press note released by Press Information Bureau, Government of India on 20th November, 2019.

⁷Fiscal deficit figure as per the revised estimation in Union Budget 2019.

⁸CASE NO.: Writ Petition (civil) 171 of 2003

disinvestment was contrary to the provisions of the laws that had nationalised these companies.⁹ But in May, 2016 government introduced the Repealing and Amending Act, 2016 and repealed all the legal roadblock so now it is possible for the government to privatise BPCL with executive action.

1.4.3 Procedure of Disinvestment in BPCL

Central government is Going to disinvest its whole share holding (i.e. 52.98 as on December 31st, 2019) along with its all subsidiaries (except 61.65% share holding in Numaligarh Refinery Limited (NRL)), Joint Ventures and Associates.

Deloitte Touche Tohmatsu India LLP (DTTILLP) has been appointed as Transaction Advisor (TA) by the Department of Investment & Public Asset Management (DIPAM) for advising on the Proposed Transaction.

The disinvestment procedure is divided into the following two stages:

1. Through this invitation for Expression of Interest (EoI), the TA is providing the Interested Parties(IP) with instructions for submitting their EoIs to the TA, which would be used for pre-qualifying the IPs in accordance with Eligibility Criteria and Disqualification conditions detailed in this invitation for EoI. Only those IPs who qualify in accordance with Eligibility Criteria and Disqualification conditions shall be allowed to participate in Stage-2 subject to IP executing Confidentiality Undertaking (CU).
2. Based on an evaluation of the EoIs submitted, the qualified IPs will be provided with Request for Proposal (RFP), and providing further details of BPCL subject to the IP executing the CU. Thereafter, financial bids submitted by the qualified IPs as per the terms of the RFP shall be opened and evaluated as per procedure laid down by GoI.

1.5 Basic Terms and Definitions

Definition 1. Public Sector Undertakings: In legislature ‘Government Company’ is termed as ‘Public Sector Undertaking’ (PSU). As per section 2(45), of the Indian Companies Act, 2013

⁹the ESSO (Acquisition of Undertaking in India) Act, 1974, the Burma Shell (Acquisition of Undertaking in India) Act, 1976 and Caltex (Acquisition of Shares of Caltex Oil Refining India Limited and all the Undertakings in India for Caltex India Limited) Act, 1977.

‘Government Company’ means any company in which not less than fifty-one per cent of the paid-up share capital is held by the Central Government, or by any State Government or Governments, or partly by the Central Government and partly by one or more State Governments, and includes a company which is a subsidiary company of such a Government company;¹⁰

Definition 2. State Owned Enterprise: Company having stack of the government is known as ‘State Owned Enterprise’ (SOE). The company having even 1% of government stack is known as SOE.

Definition 3. The Maharatnas: Maharatna Scheme was introduced for CPSEs, with effect from 19th May, 2010, in order to empower mega CPSEs to expand their operations and emerge as global giants. PSUs having Navratna status, listed on the Indian stock exchange, with a minimum prescribed public shareholding under SEBI regulations, having an average annual turnover of more than Rs. 20,000 Crore during the last three years, having an average annual net worth of more than Rs.10,000 Crore during the last three years, having an average annual net profit of more than Rs. 2,500 Crore during the last 3 years and having significant global presence or international operations are eligible for the Maharatna Status.¹¹

Definition 4. Privatisation: According to Ramesh Singh (2018) ‘Privatisation’ is a process under which the state assets were transferred to the private sector. In many literature the term privatisation is used when government sells all the stack into company along-with management and control in private capital market to the private company. After privatisation government does not have voting right in the company.

Definition 5. Disinvestment: The term ‘Disinvestment’ is used when government sells part of its stack in the company. Many times Privatisation (See definition 4 and disinvestment are considered synonyms but they are not. Unlike privatisation, state retains voting power post disinvestment.

Definition 6. Strategic Sale: Transactions involving sales made by the Government of CPSEs, including subsidiary of CPSEs, along with transfer of management control, to a strategic private partner identified through a process of competitive bidding and subsequent sales to the partner

¹⁰Though there is a thin line difference in the meaning, we are using the words Government Company, Public Sector Undertakings (PSU), Central Public Sector Enterprise (CPSE) and State Owned Enterprise (SOE) as they are synonymous.

¹¹<http://www.bsepsu.com/maharatnas.asp>

through call/put options. In short, when government sales its assets directly to the private company it is known as 'Strategic Sale'. Some authors refers strategic sale as 'True Privatisation' as most of the time it involves selling of more than 26% stack to the private company. Most of the time government uses strategic sale to its stack in listed companies.

Definition 7. Share Issue Privatisation:The term 'Share Issue Privatisation'(SIP) is used when government sells its stack in any company to the public in public capital market through Initial Public Offering (IPO) or through Further Public Offering (FPO). In other words transactions involving sales made by the Government in CPSEs through a Public Offer. Many authors refer SIP as 'Disinvestment'. In SIP government sells less than 26% of its assets in the capital market. Most of the time government uses SIP to its stack in listed companies.

Definition 8. Core Assets: Fixed assets directly used in companies operations is known as 'Core Assets'

Definition 9. Non-Core Assets: Fixed assets directly used in companies operations is known as 'Non-Core Assets'

Definition 10. Reserve Price: 'Reserve Price'is the threshold amount below which the seller generally perceives any offer or bid inadequate. Reserve Price in case of sale of a company is determined by carrying out valuation of the company.

Definition 11. Free Cash Flow: 'Free Cash Flows'(FCF) is an amount including all inflows and outflows associated with the project prior to debt service, such as taxes, amount invested in working capital and capital expenditure.

Definition 12. Fiscal Deficit: is the difference between the Revenue Receipts plus Non-debt Capital Receipts (NDCR) and the total expenditure. FD is reflective of the total borrowing requirements of Government. ¹²

1.6 Characterisation

Chapter I titled **Introduction** deals with theoretical concepts of disinvestment, disinvestment in India, BPCL and the decision of the government to privatise BPCL.

Chapter II captioned **Literature Review** summarises the previous theoretical as well as

¹²Definition given in Union Budget 2020-21

empirical studies regarding disinvestment and the research gap in those studies.

Chapter III entitled **Research Methodology** deals with objectives, hypothesis, methodology, source of information, statistical tools and techniques and the limitations of the research work.

Chapter IV christened **Data Analysis, Interpretation and Presentation** deals with analysis and interpretation part of the research.

Chapter V consolidates **Conclusions and Suggestions** summarises summary, findings, hypothesis testing, suggestions and conclusion of the research.

Followed by Appendices, Bibliography and Annexures.

Chapter 2

Literature Review

2.1 Introduction

This chapter of the research deals with the summery past researches, studies and research gaps. This chapter is divided into three parts: in first part theories related to privatisation is summarised; in the second part empirical studies are explained and in the third part research gap is analysed.

2.2 Theoretical Studies

2.2.1 Property Right Theory

Jensen & Meckling (1976) in their study titled 'Theory of the Firm: Managerial Behaviour, Agency Costs and Ownership Structure.' focuses on the 'Property Right Theory'. They stats that under state ownership agency problem faced by the company is more as managers in public sector are not monitored and incentivised. Besides, SOEs are not publicly traded and hence not vulnerable to the threat of takeover. This reinforces the poor level of monitoring. Thus, from the perspective of the property rights school, inefficiency in SOEs arises from the failure to clearly assign property rights.or, to put it differently, politicians and bureaucrats, who are vested with the job of monitoring on behalf of the public at large are not as good at such monitoring or at designing incentive systems as are shareholders in a private company (though very often, institutional shareholders perform the monitoring role on behalf of small investors).

2.2.2 Property Choice Theory

Shleifer & Vishny (1996) in their study titled 'A Survey of Corporate Governance.' focuses on the 'Property Choice Theory'. They argue that in the private sector, managers in the public sector might lack focus because they are expected to pursue a variety of objectives, not all of which are calculated to maximise profit. Multiplicity of objectives arises from the fact that public-sector managers are answerable to different constituencies, such as legislators, civil servants and ministers, each with its own objective. In particular, politicians, who are answerable to constituencies such as labour, would tend to push public-sector managers to pursue objectives, such as an increase in employment, that militate against profit maximisation.

The problem is bad enough with benevolent politicians in so far as incentives for managers to reduce costs are weak. With malevolent politicians, which some would say is the norm, costs are actively increased for firms because of politicians' desire to cultivate particular constituencies.

2.2.3 Theory of Incomplete Contract

Shleifer (1998) in his study titled 'State Versus Private Ownership.' talks about the 'Theory of Incomplete Contract'. He approaches the ownership question from the perspective of the theory of incomplete contracts. Where government can write complete contracts, specifying exactly what it wants, ownership does not matter. The problem arises where contracts are incomplete with respect to 'quality'. As he puts it, 'The choice of public versus private provision depends on how different ownership patterns affect the incentives to deliver this non-contractible quality, as well as on the cost of such delivery.'

Shleifer argues that incentives to reduce costs or to innovate and improve quality are weak when assets are publicly owned, which takes us back to the problem of incentives raised by agency theory. Public ownership would make sense only where high-powered incentives to reduce costs might impact adversely on quality.

2.3 Empirical Studies

Galal, Jones, Tandon, and Vogelsang (1994) studies set of case studies in their research titled 'Welfare Consequences of Selling Public Enterprises', involving 12 privatised firms in four countries. This study stands out in the literature for two reasons. First, the authors compare

the performance after privatisation with the 'counterfactual', i.e., the predicted performance of the firms had they not been privatised. This is in contrast to the more standard approach in which the performance post-privatisation is compared with that before privatisation.

Second, the authors do not use financial measures of performance preferred by most studies on privatisation. Instead, they compute the net change in welfare at the privatised firms, defined as the sum of the changes in welfare of consumers, enterprise profits (including effects on buyers, the government and other shareholders), welfare of labour, and welfare of competitors. They conclude: 'Did divestiture make the world world a better place, or not? In our twelve cases, this question is answered with a surprisingly uniform and resounding, "yes"'.

Authors attempt an explanation as to why studies of privatisation come to contradictory conclusions. One reason is that some of the studies compare competitive enterprises in the private sector with monopoly enterprises in the public sector, and, not surprisingly, find superior performance in the former category.

Second, some find private-sector performance legitimately superior because they are comparing reasonably competitive enterprises, and small public enterprises in a competitive situation cannot be expected to do better than private enterprises. Third, some of the studies compare public and private monopolies, and this is an area where, as the authors put it, 'the results are all over the map'.

Meggison, Nash and Randenborgh (1994) in their study titled 'The Financial and Operating Performance of Newly Privatised Firms: An International Empirical Analysis.', they focused exclusively on firms privatised through the public offer route; it did not consider firms privatised through asset sales at all. Further – and this is something that not many who cited this study seem to have noted – in all the parameters that were used to evaluate post-privatisation performance, the number of partially privatised firms exceeded the number of fully privatised firms.

On most parameters, partially privatised firms too showed improvement in performance. The notion that privatisation is effective only when a controlling stake is transferred to a private buyer through the asset (or strategic) sale route or when majority ownership by government is shed, is thus not supported by the enormous empirical literature on privatisation.

La Porta and Lopez-De-Silanes (1999) in their study titled 'The benefits of privatisation:

evidence from Mexico deals with experience of Mexico to the Privatisation. Their findings are diametrically opposite to those of the study mentioned above. The study covered 218 firms in 26 different sectors, privatised between 1983 and 1991. The authors examined seven broad indicators of performance: profitability; operating efficiency; employment and wages; capital investment; total output; prices; and taxes. The authors decomposed the gains into three components: increase in prices; reduction in workers; and productivity gains.

Meggison, Nash, Netter & Schwartz(2000) in their study titled 'The Long-Run Return to Investors in Share Issue Privatisation.' shows the impact of privatisation looks at long-run stock performance in SIPs. they reviewed large sample of SIPs across several countries.

The authors examine the returns to domestic, international and US investors who purchased shares at the first open-market price in 158 SIPs from 33 countries during the period 1981–97. They calculate buy-and-hold returns over a one-, three- and five-year period. They find that SIP investors earn higher returns than do investors who buy on the local, world or US market, or who buy a portfolio of industry-matched returns. The results are striking because the authors look at SIP returns for three different groups of investors. They consider domestic investors who purchase SIP shares in the local market and compare the returns they earn with the return they could have earned on the national market index. They look at international investors' returns on an SIP and compare these with what they could have earned on a world market index. Finally, they examine returns to a US investor from a SIP and compare these with what the investor could have earned by investing either in the S&P 500 index or the stock of an American company in the same industry as that of the firm being privatised.

The authors validate the results obtained above by using three other measures of relative performance. One is a wealth relative, which says how much money would have to be invested in the reference index or matched-firm portfolio to provide the same total return as investing one dollar (or one unit of local currency) in the SIP sample. Another is the percentage of SIP issues with holding period returns in excess of the reference index or matching-firm portfolio. The third is one-, three- and five-year compound annual returns for the SIPs compared to the country index, world index, the S&P 500, and industry-matched firms. In all cases, the SIPs outperform the reference indices and matching portfolios over all three time horizons considered.

The paper by Meggison et al. thus reinforces the conclusion of studies that use measures of financial performance: SIPs do work, no matter that governments may be retaining majority

control. Or, to put it differently, it is not necessary that governments transfer control to a private party through an asset sale in order to secure improvement in firm performance.

Meggison & Netter (2001) in their study titled ‘From State to Market: A Survey of Empirical Studies on Privatisation.’ measure changes in performance across four different periods: nationalisation; pre-privatisation (the period preceding the announcement of privatisation); post-announcement (the period following the announcement of privatisation); post-privatisation.

In this study they conclude that in nationalisation period and in pre-privatisation period the employees work efficiently and this efficiency is reflected in financial performance. In post-announcement period employee efficiency decreases as they are uncertain about their future job security. The other reason for the poor performance is that they want to show that after privatisation their efficiency is increased to get benefits of incentives. In post privatisation period their performance would be at normal efficiency but perceived relatively more efficient than the post-announcement period because of the said reasons. The longer the gap between post announcement period and post privatisation period, the lesser the efficiency of the employees in SOE during that period.

T T Ram Mohan(2003) in his research paper titled ‘Strategic sale versus public offer: dispelling myths’talks about misconception related to strategic sale and false comparison. He explains various types of auctions and their limitations. He compares SIP method of privatisation and strategic sales and arrives at the conclusion that the short term price movement of share prices (in case of listed SOEs) are not indicating the better financial performance in future but reflects merely the expectations of the public that SOE would perform better in private hands.

Meggison, Nash, Netter & Poulsen (2004) in their research titled ‘The Choice of Private Versus Public Capital Markets: Evidence from Privatisations.’find that country generally prefer SIP over strategic sale for disinvestment. .Using a sample of 2477 sales of SOEs from 108 countries that raised \$1.2 trillion between 1977 and 2000, the authors analysed the choice between raising funds in public versus private capital markets (the latter involving asset sales to private buyers).The larger proportion of proceeds was accounted for SIPs, \$745 billion (62.6 per cent), with asset sales accounting for \$445 billion (37.4 per cent).

The authors’key findings may be highlighted. First, SIPs tend to be larger in size than asset sales.The average SIP was found to generate \$794 million (median of \$105 million), whereas asset sales have average proceeds of \$289 million (median of \$31 million).Second,the portion

of an SOE privatised tends to be smaller in an SIP than in an asset sale. In the average SIP, governments sell 35 per cent of the SOE's capital. The average asset sale involves sale of 74 per cent of the government's equity in the SOE, with a median value of 90 per cent, which suggests that governments are more likely to use asset sales in order to relinquish majority ownership. Third, the proportion of government equity sold is smaller in an SIP because the enterprises concerned are very large: the average enterprise value is more than \$4.6 billion in SIPs compared to \$641 million in asset sales.

Why or under what circumstances would one method of sale be preferred to the other? Megginson and others use three types of variables to explain the choice of the means of privatisation: market characteristics, political and legal characteristics, and firm-specific characteristics. They find that governments of countries with less-developed capital markets are more likely to use SIPs, possibly as a means for developing capital markets. A more equal income distribution better conduces to SIPs because it makes for a broader base of potential investors and reduces the need for substantial under-pricing. The less the state control of the economy and the more stable the government, the greater are the chances that asset sales would be used, as investors who need to make substantial commitments would be more confident about doing so. SIPs are, however, more frequent when there are stronger protections in place for minority interests. As for the last determinant, firm-specific characteristics, the authors find that the larger and more profitable the enterprise, the greater the likelihood that SIPs would be used – a point that is worth noting when sales of large firms such as the oil majors is considered in India.

T T Ram Mohan(2005) in his book titled 'Privatisation in India: Challenging Economic Orthodoxy'talks about privatisation in Indian context in depth. By stating theories and giving many example with empirical data he proves that privatisation in profitable PSU are not advisable.

2.4 Research Gap

The major limitation of the studies is they think public ownership and privatisation is 100 per cent government-owned entities with no traded stock. While this may have been true of SOEs in the transition economies, it does not hold true in China and India. Many SOEs are listed on the exchanges and a portion of the stock is owned by retail as well as institutional shareholders, including foreign investors. The counterpart in the private sector to the stereotype of the SOE

is a firm that is 100 per cent owned by an individual.

In India, where large firms are concerned, there is one large shareholder, either the government or an industrial family, who holds the largest or the majority stake, with the rest of the shares being held by institutional and retail shareholders. In both SOEs and industrial houses, there are professional managers controlled by the dominant shareholder, the government in one case and the industrial family in the other. It is hard to see why one form is intrinsically superior to the other in respect of governance.

As the argument is claiming the advantage that private ownership is said to enjoy, its being subject to the discipline of the market for corporate control, which is stronger than any discipline that politicians and bureaucrats might impose on SOEs. If private sector managers fail to maximise shareholder wealth, they will be duly disciplined by the capital market. Shareholders will sell under-performing shares, causing prices to fall and creating conditions for a takeover by another firm. But this argument is invalid as we have seen in the paragraphs above that the large firm in private sectors are generally owned by the industrial family (especially in India) so despite the under-performance of the company the company would not be sold. The other reason is that the transaction cost for selling more stock in the company is more and many times other firms don't have enough fund so that they can tack over the large under-performing private firm.

The other limitation is that when the argument of incentive to the managers in Indian context is wrong as in India government employees are given many monetary and non-monetary benefits. So if we talk about the managerial level designation in the SOE there is no doubt about the lack of motivation because of lack of incentives.

Chapter 3

Research Methodology

3.1 Objectives

The followings are the objectives for the study :

- To critically analyse the decision of privatising BPCL.
- To judge whether the privatisation in BPCL will improve its financial performance or not.
- To assess whether the privatisation in BPCL will help in meeting fiscal gap in the economy.
- To evaluate the strategic sale method of privatisation and the issues related to valuation in this method.
- To offer remedial suggestions, if any, as the study may warrant.

3.2 Hypotheses

The followings are the null hypothesis for the study :

- Privatisation of profit making CPSE like BPCL is not justified.
- Privatisation does not ensure better financial performance.
- Privatisation is not a desirable step to meet fiscal gap.
- Privatisation through strategic sale is not a desirable step.

3.3 Methodology

The main objective of this research work is to judge whether the privatisation in BPCL is desirable or not (see 3.1 Objectives). To check its desirability, we need to know what will be consequences if the BPCL is privatised, and what will be consequences if it is not. So, this research is dealing with future aspects of the company in financial terms as well as its impact on the Indian economy in the future. The analysis part of the study (Chapter 4 Data Analysis, Interpretation and Presentation) is divided into three parts:

1. Evaluation of Financial Performance,
2. Evaluation of Impact on the Indian Economy and
3. Evaluation of Strategic Sale Method of Privatisation

The methodologies used for these three analysis are different. Let's see them one by one.

3.3.1 Methodology Used for Evaluation of Financial Performance

The future financial data used in the study is extrapolated from the last 11 years data. The extrapolation is done with 'Liner Regression Model with Intercept' and 'Liner Regression Model without Intercept'. The detailed notes on these two models is given further in this chapter (see section 3.7 Statistical Tools Employed). Future data in case of 'if BPCL is not privatised is derived simply from extrapolating last 11 years data (from 2008-09 to 2018-19) with both the regression model; but in case of 'if BPCL is privatised the future data relating to the company is derived by replicating the slop of the trend line of Reliance Industries Limited (RIL) to the BPCL (for regression model without intercept) and replicating the slop of the trend line of RIL to the BPCL without changing intercept of the trend line of the BPCL. The reason to take RIL data as the base is that, RIL is the public company with nearly zero per cent government stack in the same segment, so we can get clear idea about the fully privatised BPCL for the future. The prediction is made for the next three years. For predicting future data with regression model, weighted average of the data (data from the 2008-09 to the previous year) is assumed as predictor or independent variable, and the current year data is assumed as prediction or dependent variable. The other sections in this chapter will help in understanding the methodology more clearly.

3.3.2 Methodology Used for Evaluation of Impact on the Indian Economy

For determining the possible impact of privatisation of BPCL, we compared the what would be the fiscal deficit deficit in both the cases (if BPCL is privatised and if BPCL is not privatised). For this comparison, we assumed certain assumptions as follows:

Assumption 1. In both the cases, GDP remains the same as stated in the Union Budget 2020-21.

Assumption 2. BPCL will distribute all its profit to its equity shareholders and retained profit would be zero.

Assumption 3. Tax receipts to the government from BPCL in both the cases would be same. (In an actual scenario tax rate for company is different under the private ownership and under the government ownership.)

Assumption 4. Interest expenses would be same in both the cases. (In actual scenario if disinvestment receipts decreases than borrowings of the government and interest expenses on that borrowings increases.)

Assumption 5. Closing market price of the share on the last trading day of the FY 2019-20 is taken as the base of calculating privatisation proceeds.

Assumption 6. Welfare expenses would be same in both the case. (In actual scenario, when any SOE is privatised and there is not any condition of retaining the employees even under the private ownership then many times it results in the lay off of the current workforce. The higher the number of the employee laid off, the higher the unemployment rate in the economy and the higher the welfare expenses for the unemployed workforce.)

Estimated Fiscal deficit in the scenario of privatising BPCL is directly borrowed from the Union Budget 2020-21. We calculated estimated fiscal deficit for the scenario if BPCL is not privatised by adding privatisation proceeds (See 3.8.2 Calculation of Privatisation Proceeds) and deducting dividend income(See 3.8.3 Calculation of Final Dividend).

3.3.3 Methodology Used for Evaluation of Strategic Sale Method of Privatisation

In this section we will compare the most widely used privatisation approaches: privatisation through public offer and privatisation through strategic sale. As the comparison using financial

analysis method, statistical method and mathematical method is very complex for this subtopic, the exploration in this topic is very limited.

In this subtopic, first we will see which approach is suitable under what circumstances. Then we will focus only on the strategic sale method as the privatisation of BPCL is done through this route. We will see why government should go with the strategic sale route (the arguments) and why government should not go with this method (the counterarguments).

3.4 Period of Analysis under Study

In this research work, data for next three years (i.e. from 2019-20 to 2022-23) is considered. For estimating this data, data of last eleven years is used as predictor (i.e. from 2008-09 to 2018-19).

3.5 Scope and Coverage

This research is primarily focusing on critically analysing the decision of CCEA of selling assets in BPCL, estimating its future financial performance and its impact on Indian economy.

3.6 Sources of the Information

As this research work is dealing with the subject of economics and finance, the data is collected from secondary sources only. The reason for not collecting data from primary source is that I am doing this research work in the month of March 2020 when government has advised to avoid social distancing (which is the basic requirement in most of the primary data collection) to stop the spread of Coronavirus Disease 2019 (COVID-19).

The sources of the data is mentioned below all the tables. The data regarding financial information of the BPCL is borrowed from the Annual Financial Reports of the Company; the data related to economy is borrowed from the Union Budget 2020-21 ; the data related to financial market is taken from the stock exchange website. information related to court orders is taken from the website of the Supreme Court of India; information related to legislative acts is taken from the ministry website; information related with the company is taken from the BPCL website; information regarding disinvestment and privatisation is taken from the website of

Department of Investment and Public Asset Management; information related to press releases is taken from PIB website. Apart from that different journals, newspaper articles, research papers, books and online encyclopedia are used to get data and information related to this study.

3.7 Statistical Tools Employed

The details of the statistical tools applied in this research work is as under:

3.7.1 Weighted Mean

Formally, the weighted mean of a non-empty finite multi-set of data $\{x_1, x_2, \dots, x_n\}$, with corresponding non-negative weights $\{w_1, w_2, \dots, w_n\}$ is

$$\bar{x} = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^n w_i x_i}{\sum_{i=1}^n w_i}, \quad (3.1)$$

which expands to:

$$\bar{x} = \frac{w_1 x_1 + w_2 x_2 + \dots + w_n x_n}{w_1 + w_2 + \dots + w_n}. \quad (3.2)$$

Therefore, data elements with a high weight contribute more to the weighted mean than do elements with a low weight. The weights cannot be negative. Some may be zero, but not all of them (since division by zero is not allowed).

3.7.2 Linear Regression Model with Intercept

The linear regression be intercept if the line regression intersection with Y axis in not origin. It means that mathematically $B_0 \neq 0$ that is intersection point of regression line with Y axis.

$$Y_i = B_0 + B_1 X_{i1} + e_i, \quad i = 1, 2, 3, \dots, n \quad (3.3)$$

Where,

Y_i = depended variable

X_{i1} = independent variable

B_0, B_1 = regression parameter

e_i = value of random error

3.7.3 Linear Regression Model without Intercept

The linear regression be without intercept when the line regression to pass through the origin. It means that mathematically $B_0 = 0$.

We can write the simple linear regression model:

$$Y_i = B_1 X_{i1} + e_i, i = 1, 2, 3, \dots, n \quad (3.4)$$

The parameters B and B usually unknown and estimate by least squares method. From equation 3.5 and 3.6

$$\hat{B}_1 = \frac{S_{xy}}{S_x} \quad (3.5)$$

$$\hat{B}_0 = \bar{Y} - \hat{B}_1 \bar{X} \quad (3.6)$$

Where,

S_{xy} = Standard deviation between X and Y

S_x = Standard deviation of X

But linear regression without intercept:

$$\hat{B}_1 = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^n X_i Y_i}{\sum_{i=1}^n X_i^2} \quad (3.7)$$

3.8 Financial Analysis Techniques Employed

The following financial analysis tools and techniques are employed in this research work:

3.8.1 Financial Ratio Analysis

For analysing whether the financial performance and efficiency of the company (BPCL) will be improved after the privatisation, the 'Financial Ratio Analysis' technique is employed. These ratios are 'Net Profit Margin', 'Net Profit to Net Worth', 'Operating Profit to Long-term Capital Employed', 'Total Expenditure to Total Income' and 'Net Sales to Net Fixed Assets'. The first three ratios are used for measuring profitability of the company and the rest of the two gives idea about efficiency of the firm. By knowing companies profitability and efficiency, we can easily get idea about the financial performance. The detailed explanation of the financial ratios are as under:

3.8.1.1 Net Profit Margin

Net Profit Margin is a profitability ratio. As the name suggests, Net Profit Margin shows how much net profit (in percentage) company is generating from the net sales. Equation 3.8 is the formula for Net Profit Margin.

$$\text{Net Profit Margin} = \frac{PAT}{\text{Net Sales}} \times 100 \quad (3.8)$$

3.8.1.2 Net Profit to Net Worth

Net Profit to Net Worth is a profitability ratio. This ratio shows how much net profit (in percentage) company is generating from fund of equity share holders. Equation 3.9 is the formula for Net Profit to Net Worth.

$$\text{Net Profit to Net Worth} = \frac{PAT}{\text{Net Worth}} \times 100 \quad (3.9)$$

3.8.1.3 Operating Profit to Long-term Capital Employed

Operating Profit to Long-term Capital Employed is a profitability ratio. This ratio shows how much operating profit (in percentage) company is generating from long-term fund. Equation 3.10 is the formula for Operating Profit to Long-term Capital Employed.

$$\text{Operating Profit to Longterm Capital Employed} = \frac{PBIT}{\text{Longterm Capital Employed}} \times 100 \quad (3.10)$$

3.8.1.4 Total Expenditure to Total Income

Total Expenditure to Total Income is a efficiency ratio. This ratio shows what is the proportion of total expenses (in percentage) out of the total income generated by the company. Equation 3.11 is the formula for Total Expenditure to Total Income

$$\text{Total Expenditure to Total Income} = \frac{\text{Total Expenditure}}{\text{Total Income}} \times 100 \quad (3.11)$$

3.8.1.5 Net Sales to Net Fixed Assets

Net Sales to Net Fixed Assets is a efficiency ratio. This ratio shows how efficiently the company in utilising its net fixed assets by comparing the net sales and net fixed assets. Equation 3.12 is the formula for Net Sales to Net Fixed Assets

$$\text{Net Sales to Net Fixed Assets} = \frac{\text{Net Sales}}{\text{Net Fixed Assets}} \times 100 \quad (3.12)$$

3.8.2 Calculation of Privatisation Proceeds

The revenue received by the government by privatising any PSU is known as privatisation proceeds which can be calculated by the formula given in the equation 3.13

$$\text{Privatisation Proceeds} = \text{Number of Equity Shares to be Sold} \times \text{Market Price per Share} \quad (3.13)$$

3.8.3 Calculation of Final Dividend

Company shares its profit to its equity share holders in the form of dividend. The dividend is paid on the face value of the share. The dividend can be interim dividend and final dividend. The calculation of final dividend is shown in equation 3.14.

$$\text{Final Dividend} = \text{PAT per Share} - \text{Interim Dividend per Share} \quad (3.14)$$

3.9 Limitations of the Research

Followings are the limitations of this project:

- As the most of the information are collected from the secondary source, the data is subjected to the biasness of the researcher.
- Estimations of future financial performance for the BPCL after privatisation are based on replication of slope of the trend equation of the RIL, so the estimation are not 100% reliable.
- Changes in laws related to presentation of financial reports and calculation of financial information affects the input data.
- Statistical methods employed for analysing the data have their own limitations.
- Abnormal events (e.g. Crude Oil Price War between Saudi Arabia and Russia, Yes Bank Crisis, impact of COVID-19, etc.) are not considered while estimating future performance.
- Savings in welfare expenses for the workforce laid off because of the privatisation, future bonus share offers, changes in the expenses of payment of interest, changes in tax revenue is not considered while calculating the estimated fiscal deficit if BPCL is not privatised.
- Limited time period for the research is also one of the limitation for this research work.
- Financial data shows the position for the FY 2018-19 while market data shows the position for the FY 2019-20. In this way data under the study is inconsistent.

Chapter 4

Data Analysis, Interpretation and Presentation

4.1 Evaluation of Financial Performance

As explained in the chapter 3 Research Methodology, to compare future financial performance of BPCL in both the case (if it is privatised and if it is not privatised), we used financial ratio analysis. Appendix 2 shows the financial information which are taken as the base to predict future financial information. The prediction is made using both the regression models (with and without intercept) for better understanding. Subsection 4.1.1 Estimation with Regression Model without Intercept deals with data predicted with Regression Model without Intercept and Subsection 4.1.2 Estimation with Regression Model without Intercept deals with data predicted with Regression Model without Intercept.

4.1.1 Estimation with Regression Model without Intercept

The result derived from Regression Model without Intercept is shown in Appendix 3 in absolute terms. The financial ratio analysis in both the future cases is shown in the Table 4.1.

Ratios	If BPCL will not be privatised			If BPCL will be privatised		
	2019-20	2020-21	2021-22	2019-20	2020-21	2021-22
Net Profit Margin	3.22%	3.45%	3.68%	2.58%	2.63%	2.68%
Net Profit to Net Worth	26.48%	27.64%	28.77%	19.85%	19.49%	19.17%
Operating Profit to Long-term Capital Employed	25.36%	26.45%	27.52%	19.60%	19.43%	19.28%
Total Expenses to Total Income	95.76%	95.59%	95.43%	95.15%	94.89%	94.64%
Net Sales to Net Fixed Assets	537.92%	512.85%	490.52%	609.50%	597.39%	586.34%

Source: Author's Calculation

Table 4.1: Financial Ratio Analysis for the Estimated Data from Regression Model without Intercept

For making comparison easy for the ratios shown in the Table 4.1 we used the Table 4.2. In this table '1' shows better position while '0' shows comparatively bad position.

Ratios	If BPCL will not be privatised				If BPCL will be privatised				Total
	2019-20	2020-21	2021-22	Total	2019-20	2020-21	2021-22	Total	
Net Profit Margin	1	1	1	3	0	0	0	0	3
Net Profit to Net Worth	1	1	1	3	0	0	0	0	3
Operating Profit to Long-term Capital Employed	1	1	1	3	0	0	0	0	3
Total Expenses to Total Income	1	1	1	3	0	0	0	0	3
Net Sales to Net Fixed Assets	0	0	0	0	1	1	1	3	3
Total	4	4	4	12	1	1	1	3	15

Source: Author's Calculation

Table 4.2: Comparison of Financial Ratios of the Estimated Data from Regression Model without Intercept

As shown in the Table 4.2, all the ratios except Net Sales to Net Fixed Assets, favours the case of not privatising BPCL for the next three years. So we can interpret it as if BPCL is not privatised its profitability would be more in comparison with the profitability in case of it is privatised. The situation would be same in context of proportion of total expenses to the total income. But in context of efficiency of utilising net fixed assets, the case of privatising BPCL is better.

4.1.2 Estimation without Regression Model with Intercept

The result derived from Regression Model without Intercept is shown in Appendix 4 in absolute terms. The financial ratio analysis in both the future cases is shown in the Table 4.3.

Ratios	If BPCL will not be privatised			If BPCL will be privatised		
	2019-20	2020-21	2021-22	2019-20	2020-21	2021-22
Net Profit Margin	3.14%	3.32%	3.51%	8.53%	10.41%	12.51%
Net Profit to Net Worth	21.95%	21.32%	20.64%	22.33%	21.67%	20.96%
Operating Profit to Long-term Capital Employed	22.22%	22.08%	21.86%	15.66%	14.00%	12.52%
Total Expenses to Total Income	95.14%	94.80%	94.47%	88.17%	88.06%	88.03%
Net Sales to Net Fixed Assets	440.16%	387.20%	341.72%	194.64%	155.56%	125.74%

Source: Author's Calculation

Table 4.3: Financial Ratio Analysis for the Estimated Data from Regression Model with Intercept

For making comparison easy for the ratios shown in the Table 4.3 we used the Table 4.4. In this table '1' shows better position while '0' shows comparatively bad position.

Ratios	If BPCL will not be privatised				If BPCL will be privatised				Total
	2019-20	2020-21	2021-22	Total	2019-20	2020-21	2021-22	Total	
Net Profit Margin	0	0	0	0	1	1	1	3	3
Net Profit to Net Worth	0	0	0	0	1	1	1	3	3
Operating Profit to Long-term Capital Employed	1	1	1	3	0	0	0	0	3
Total Expenses to Total Income	1	1	1	3	0	0	0	0	3
Net Sales to Net Fixed Assets	1	1	1	3	0	0	0	0	3
Total	3	3	3	9	2	2	2	6	15

Source: Author's Calculation

Table 4.4: Comparison of Financial Ratios of the Estimated Data from Regression Model with Intercept

As shown in the Table 4.4, Net Profit Margin and Net Profit to Net Worth favour the case of privatising BPCL, and all the other ratios are favouring the case of not privatising BPCL. The result shows the case of privatising BPCL would bring improved efficiency while the of not privatising BPCL would bring better profitability.

4.1.3 Analysis

Subsection 4.1.1 shows that 12 out of 15 parameters favour the case of not privatising BPCL. More precisely, all the profitability ratios are in the favour of the case of not privatising BPCL and the efficiency ratio gives neutral view for both the cases.

Subsection 4.1.2 shows that 9 out of 15 parameters favour the case of not privatising BPCL. All the efficiency ratios one out of three profitability ratios are in the favour of not privatising BPCL.

Estimation of the both the models gives the same results in the context of two ratios (i.e., Operating Profit to Long-term Capital Employed and Total Expenses to Total Income) but the other ratios are giving opposite conclusion in both the models. So, we can say that if the BPCL is not privatised, operating profit would be high and total expenses would be low. Though we can expect better profitability and better efficiency in the case of not privatising BPCL as most of the ratios (21 out of 30) are favouring that case.

Many authors proved from empirical data that privatisation improves the efficiency, though most of them are failed to give specific reason for improved efficiency after privatisation. T. T. Ram Mohan (2005) explores the reasons behind better performance after the privatisation. According to him there are mainly three reasons for improvement in efficiency under the private ownership:

1. Lay off of the employees (Which results in reduced labour cost and increase in per employee revenue.)
2. Increase in product price while cost remaining unchanged (Which results in higher profit margin.)
3. More productivity due to higher efficiency

Most of the authors and government always highlights the third reasons but the first two reasons are always kept hidden to argue in support of privatisation.

4.2 Evaluation of Impact on the Indian Economy

When the government is unable to reduce unproductive expenditure nor is it able to raise tax revenues it results into fiscal deficit. Generally, fiscal deficit is bridged by additional money

supply by the central bank of the nation or by borrowing from the public. Additional money supply leads to inflation while borrowing leads to higher interest rates and crowding out of private investment as shown in IS-LM framework. Both the situation are not desirable for the economy. In addition to this, borrowing will also be resulted in higher interest payment for the government.

As mentioned in the press note released by PIB on November 20, 2019, one objective of BPCL privatisation is to unlock resources blocked in BPCL and utilise them in financing social sectors/ developmental programmes which will benefit the public. But if we see the past, most of the time government has utilised this proceeds not in developing physical, social and legal infrastructure but to meet fiscal pressure. If the privatisation proceeds are used to bridge the fiscal deficit, it reduces pressure on government to cut expenditure or raise taxes. This merely defers the fiscal problem, it does not mitigate it.

By privatising any PSU government get the proceeds (which is very big in case of privatisation of BPCL) but it has to give up the future earnings from that PSU. If the PSU is loss making or giving less earning than the proceeds of its privatisation, then the privatisation is justified. But if we are talking about profit making PSU like BPCL which is not only generating dividend income (See Appendix 5 and Appendix 6) but also giving the bonus shares (See Appendix 7). Profit making entity like BPCL also contributes to the net worth of the government by steady growth in its market capitalisation.

The other reason why privatisation of BPCL is not justified for macroeconomic scenario is that a huge number of employees are dependent on BPCL. The one of the main objective of any PSU is to generate and retain higher employment and if BPCL is ceased to be a PSU, many of the employees and workers may loss the jobs. The rise in unemployment will increase expenditure for welfare of the unemployed work force in the some way or in the other way.

4.2.1 Proceeds from Privatisation

Following the method we discussed prior to this chapter, the estimated proceeds government would get from privatising BPCL will be:

$$1, 14, 91, 83, 592 \text{ Shares} \times ₹ 316.05 = ₹ 3, 63, 19, 94, 74, 251$$

4.2.2 Future Dividend

By observing appendix 2 and 6, we can say that BPCL is giving final as well as interim dividend to its equity share holders every year. From the profit of the FY 2019-20 interim dividend has already been offered at the rate 165% on the face value of the share which is ₹10 per share and total number of share outstanding in 2,16,92,52,744 share (See Table 1.2. So total amount of interim dividend is:

Total Amount Paid as Interim Dividend

$$= ₹10 \times 2,16,92,52,744 \text{ share} \times 165\% = ₹35,79,26,70,276 \cong ₹3,579 \text{ Crore}$$

Now to get the amount of final dividend for the FY 2019-20 we can get by deducting amount of interim dividend from PAT for the FY 2019-20. The amount (estimated) of PAT for the FY 2019-20 is ₹9,742 Crore (by using regression model without intercept for estimation, see Appendix 3) and ₹9,394 Crore (by using regression model with intercept for estimation, see Appendix 4). By considering principal of conservatism of accounting, we will use ₹9,394 Crore for further calculation.

Estimated Amount of Final Dividend =

$$₹9,394 \text{ Crore} - ₹3,579 \text{ Crore} = ₹5,816 \text{ Crore}$$

4.2.3 Fiscal Deficit

As per the Union Budget 2020-21, the estimated fiscal deficit is ₹7,96,337 Crore (i.e. 3.5% of GDP). In the budget GDP is estimated at ₹2,24,89,420 Crore.

Particulars	Amount (in ₹Crore)
Estimated Fiscal Deficit if BPCL is Privatised	7,96,337
Add: Disinvestment proceeds from BPCL	36,319
Less: Final Dividend	(5,816)
Estimated Fiscal Deficit if BPCL is not Privatised	8,26,880

Source: Author's Calculation

Table 4.5: Estimated Fiscal Deficit if BPCL is not Privatised

From the Table 4.5, we can see that if BPCL is not privatised then the fiscal deficit will be of ₹8,26,880 Crore (i.e. 3.7%).

4.2.4 Analysis

As shown in subsection above, the fiscal deficit if BPCL is not privatised is 3.7% of GDP and if it is privatised, the fiscal deficit would be 3.5% of GDP as stated in Union Budget 2020-21. If BPCL is continued to be a CPSE than fiscal deficit of our economy would be higher by 0.2 percentage point of GDP which is ₹44,979 Crore in absolute terms.

But here, we should note that in calculation of fiscal deficit we have not considered the savings in welfare expenses for the workforce laid off because of the privatisation, future bonus share offers, changes in the expenses of payment of interest, changes in tax revenue. We should also keep in mind that if we get that proceeds from privatisation, then it would one time event only; and in contrary to that if BPCL is not privatised then government will receive dividend every year. BPCL is giving final dividend to its equity share holders at the rate 105% of face value (weighted average) and interim dividend at the rate 165% of face value (weighted average) every year. So if we give the effect of future dividend for the next few years and other variables (savings in welfare expenses for the workforce laid off because of the privatisation, future bonus share offers, changes in the expenses of payment of interest, changes in tax revenue) in the calculation of the fiscal deficit, then we can surly say that fiscal deficit would be less than 3.7% (even less than 3.5%).

4.3 Evaluation of Strategic Sale Method of Privatisation

The two most prevalent approaches of privatisation are 'Strategic Sales'(See definition 6 Strategic Sales) and 'Public Offer'(See definition 7 Public Offer). Government has chosen the strategic sale approach of privatisation for BPCL. The process of strategic sale involves inviting expressions of interest from interested parties, followed by a short-listing based on certain eligibility criteria and invitation of bids from those short-listed. The highest bidder wins out provided his offer is higher than a reserve price (See definition 10 Reserve Price) set by the government (which is not known to bidders).In this section we will analyse strategic sales route in depth.

4.3.1 Suitability of Strategic Sale and Share Issue Privatisation

Table 4.6 shows the suitability of strategic sale and share issue privatisation (SIP) on certain basis:

Basis	Strategic Sale	Share Issue Privatisation
Capital Market Characteristics	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> This method is suitable in the economy where capital market has already developed. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> This method is suitable in the economy where capital market is not developed that much. SIP injects the new shares in the stock exchange and encourage public to trade in capital market.
Firm-specific Characteristics	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> This method is suitable for the small or loss making companies. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> This method is suitable for large and profit making companies.
Political and Legal Characteristics	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> This route is preferable for the nation with political stability. Investor who is going for large commitment can be more confident if the political condition of the nation is stable. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> This route is preferable for the nation with stronger legal protection for its minority share holders.
Residual Holding with the Government after Disinvestment	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> This method is suitable when after disinvestment government is of holding majority shares in the company. Majority government holding after disinvestment would retain public confidence in the firm. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> This method is suitable when after disinvestment government holding is of minority shares in the company. Minority government holding after disinvestment would result in more efficient performance with less political interference.

Table 4.6: Suitability of Strategic Sale and Share Issue Privatisation

4.3.2 Arguments and Counterarguments for Strategic Sale

After understanding the suitability of the methods, now we will see the arguments for strategic sales and counterarguments for strategic sales are as under:

Argument 1. The valuation is carried out by independent adviser such as investment banker (See Annexure I Valuation Methodology in Strategic Sale to understand various reserve price valuation methods), so reserve price has to be unbiased and objective.

Counterargument 1. Independent adviser have an obvious interest in seeing sales go through because their fee is linked to a sale being consummated and have, therefore, every incentive to undervalue government assets. The incentive would be even stronger where the government is keen to ensure that the transaction goes through, whether for ideological or revenue considerations. Moreover, many investment banks have close business associations with the bidding parties in the private sector and this too could be expected to create a bias towards undervaluation.

Argument 2. This method must lead to superior efficiency because an asset is being transferred to a buyer who clearly places a higher valuation on it compared to its value under government ownership.

Counterargument 2. The valuation of the company would not be higher if there is a condition for private entity to retain the workforce even after the privatisation (As the case in Air India Privatisation). The other case is incorrect valuation, if the reserve price is undervalued than there is chance that company is sold in less value. In the opposite case, overvalued reserve price, though the bids are accurately set, they would not be proved sufficient against overvalued reserve price.

Argument 3. Apart from valuation through methodology stated in 5.6 Valuation Methodology in Strategic Sales, last few years share price is also considered. So there is least chance of incorrect valuation.

Counterargument 3. If the company is unlisted (which is normal scenario for strategic sale) or capital market is depressed (2020 stock market crash because of COVID-19) than it would not be helpful to take share price as supplement of valuation method.

Argument 4. Certain criterion and shortlisting are done for the company to invite them for bidding in strategic sale. This type of filtering will help in smooth conduct of the process and

for maximising the revenue.

Counterargument 4. Many times SOEs are not allowed to bid for other SOE (which is the case with BPCL) which results in lower revenue as private sector company does not have that much of the fund as SOE. So it narrows the scope.

Argument 5. According to 'Revenue Maximisation Theorem', bidders in strategic sales are risk-averse and not risk-neutral. All the bidders have one goal to buy the company and all the bidders take maximum risk to buy the company. As all the bidders are risk-averse, seller will generate maximum revenue.

Counterargument 5. The argument of being risk-averse of bidders does not seem true in actual scenario as there is difference in the degree of risk averseness amongst all the bidders. The other reason is that there is no guarantee that the risk-averse bidder estimates fair value in his bid e.g. bidder who takes more risk with overvalued bid amount will get the company against the bidder taking low risk with fair valuation.

Argument 6. In auction to sale the PSU, all the bidders update their amount of bid with interaction to other bidders. These updates in the bid amount will result into the higher revenue for the seller.

Counterargument 6. The argument of co-related value or updates in the bids are true for 'English Auctions'. But in India, the government uses 'First Price Sealed Auction'. In this auction bidders first bid is the final bid and they can not alter the amount of their bid which makes the co-relation of the value and recognition of maximum value false.

Argument 7. In first price sealed bid auction method for strategic sale, more private companies are encouraged to bid as their bid amount is kept anonymous.

Counterargument 7. If the bidders are shortlisted with certain criterion then the encouragement for more bidders in the auction fails as one side the government is encouraging the private companies to bid in the auctions by keeping their bid amount anonymous and on the other side it is imposing some conditions to participate in the auction.

Argument 8. Strategic sale is win-win situation for all the parties involved. The company having knowledge of the business of PSU will try to buy the PSU at any price and in this way the bidding firm win the auction. PSU would be benefited as it will go under the efficient private hand. The private company having no or less information about the business of the PSU would

not bid high and in this way by losing the auction this private company can save huge amount of money from the business it does not have business knowledge.

Counterargument 8. Contrary to argument imposed above, there are the chance that the company having more information about the business of PSU may loss in auction and company having less information about the business of PSU may win as all the companies are not knowing each others bid and can alter the bid price. It can be happen when company having knowledge of PSU business bid less aggressively and their counterparts bid more aggressively. Sometimes it also results in ‘Winner Curse’(i.e, winner thinks that she bid more amount than the actual value) and it results in loss for all the parties. The company having knowledge of the PSU business can not buy the PSU as their bid price is low; the winner (Company having less or even no knowledge of the PSU business)- despite of paying more amount, it can not manage the company efficiently and the PSU- as it would go in wrong hands.

4.3.3 Analysis

After knowing the suitability of strategic sales in the Table 4.6 and studying arguments and counterarguments in this section, we can now easily understand that the strategic sale method in the privatisation of BPCL in appropriate or not.

If we see the Indian financial market or Indian capital market, it is still not developed that much. A large population in India is still unaware about the investment in equity shares. At this time, by offering shares of profitable PSU like BPCL Petroleum Corporation Limited to the public, government can gain confidence of public in financial market. So, it is more appropriate to go with SIP route rather than strategic sale route to privatise BPCL.

If we see it from the firm specific characteristic view point, it is also favouring SIP mode as BPCL is large and profitable PSU. It is more beneficial for our economy if we invite general public to take part in our future profit rather than any private firm.

If we see the empirical evidence in the Indian context, average proceeds government gets from company privatised with SIP route is ₹2611.89 Crore against ₹164.44 Crore with strategic sale method; the proportion disinvested with SIP is smaller (average 9.87%) against strategic sale (average 76.28%). (See Appendix 8 to Appendix 17 for the input data of the calculation.) Though disinvestment of smaller proportion, SIP is generating higher proceeds than the strategic sales. So we can say that SIP route is also better route for revenue maximisation.

There is also chance of undervaluation in reserve price if we consider market value of the share as base as the Indian stock market is suffering from many abnormal events like 2020 stock market crash due to COVID-19, Crude Oil Price War and Yes Bank Crisis.

The government has narrowed the scope of auction bidding as in BPCL privatisation other SEOs are not allowed to participate. It will also reduce competition in auction and proceeds too.

Like any other strategic sale in India, this privatisation is also following the way of anonymous bidding which restricts the bidders to alter their bidding amount in co-relation to the other bidders in the auction.

After analysing these much point, we can conclude that it is better for our economy and for the company at this stage not to go with strategic sale method. SIP route is more suitable for this privatisation.

Chapter 5

Conclusions and Suggestions

5.1 Summery of the Study

In this study, we saw that what is disinvestment; how it is different from privatisation; different approaches and different methods of disinvestment; what is the strategic sale and its environment. We also saw the disinvestment in the context of India. We tried to understand why BPCL is important as a PSU for the Indian Economy. BPCL is expected to generate disinvestment revenue of ₹60,000 Crore from the strategic sale¹.

We took a look of prior studies. Some of them are theoretical in the nature and some of them are empirical in their nature. Most of these research work carried out with the assumption that PSU holding is 100% government but in realty it is traded on stock exchange and the stack of non-government listed public company is not dominated by a particular group of people but in Indian scenario these enterprises not only traded on stock exchange, but also dominated by an industrial family. We tried to find out the research gaps.

BY employing certain statistical techniques we estimated future financial performance of the BPCL in both the condition- if it is privatised and if it is not privatised. We also estimated the impact on macro economy due to privatisation of BPCL.

We tried to find out the answers of some questions like, whether the privatisation in BPCL will improve its financial performance or not; whether the privatisation in BPCL will help in meeting fiscal gap in the economy; whether the strategic sale is a good method for disinvestment

¹expected revenue as per the market price on November 20, 2019 the date of approval of disinvestment.

in BPCL or not and is it a good decision to privatise BPCL or not.

5.2 Findings of the Study

With the help of theoretical concepts, empirical data, statistical tools and techniques, we analysed the research problem in depth. The followings are the findings of the research work:

1. BPCL is giving better profits and efficiency under the government ownership. Out of 30 parameters we studied, BPCL out performs 21 under the state ownership. But the result is giving contradictory results if we compare it with the results of other empirical research work. Many of the PSUs performed better after the privatisation. But we see the reasons of better this performance under the private ownership, it can be either lay off of the work force or increase in the price of the output or better management or the combination of all. So we can say that, BPCL is performing financial well under the government ownership and at the same time.
2. Privatisation of BPCL will help government reducing the fiscal deficit by approximately 0.2 percentage point. But the benefit is short term in nature. Economy can gain more from the dividend rather than disinvestment revenue in long run. In this way, it is more beneficial for our economy not to privatise BPCL.
3. Though it will take more time if we go with share issue method of privatisation, but empirical study suggests that this method generates more revenue against strategic sale method. Not only that, SIP would help the Indian Capital Market as it is still not developed. Moreover, it is advisable to share the ownership and profit of the profitable company with the general public rather than sharing it with private player. So, it is better to privatise BPCL through SIP method.

5.3 Hypothesis Testing

The following are the result of hypothesis (See 3.2 Hypothesis) testing:

- It is proven that privatisation of profit making CPSE like BPCL is not justified.
- It is proven that privatisation does not ensure better financial performance.

- It is proven that privatisation is not a desirable step to meet fiscal gap.
- It is proven that privatisation through strategic sale is not a desirable step.

5.4 Suggestions

My suggestions on the disinvestment in BPCL are as follows:

1. If government want to unlock the resources blocked in the PSUs, it is better to privatise loss making PSUs as the contribution of profit making PSU would more in the Indian economy if it is not privatised.
2. If government want to privatise the BPCL, strategic sale is not the advisable method. Government should privatise BPCL by the way of SIP.

5.5 Scope for the Further Studies

This research work has some limitations. This limitations can be eliminated from the following studies:

- Opinions of well known economists on BPCL privatisation
- Impact of Crude Oil Price War between Saudi Arabia and Russia on BPCL Privatisation.
- Impact of COVID-19 pandemic on BPCL Privatisation.

5.6 Conclusion

We have seen many times the opportunity cost of the economic resources confined in the PSUs are quite high. But it not the case with BPCL though government is going to privatise BPCL. We should understand that loss making PSUs should be disinvested if the argument is to make the firm more profitable & efficient not an already competitive & efficient firm. It is pessimistic thinking of government if government is thinking that it is better to privatise BPCL when it is performing well and before it starts worse performance. It is also not good if government is trying to bridge fiscal gap by disinvestment. The strategic sale method of disinvestment is also arousing doubts is it the only reason to release the resources quickly to bridge fiscal gaps.

In my opinion, government should disinvest a loss making CPSE and not profit making PSU like BPCL. Moreover, the disinvestment should be carry out with SIP method and not strategic sale method.

Appendices

Appendix1

Description of Variables Used in the Study

Variable	Description
PAT	PBT - Tax
Net Sale	Revenue - Indirect Taxes
PBIT	PBT + Finance Cost (or Interest Paid)
Net Worth	Equity Share Capital + Reserves and Surplus
Long Term Capital Employed	Net Worth + Non Current Liabilities
Total Expenses	Expenses excluding Tax Expenses
Total Income	Revenue from Operations + Other Revenues
Net Fixed Assets	Non Current Assets - Financial Assets
Market Capitalisation	Market Price per Share × Number of Shares Outstanding

Appendix1: Description of Variables Used in the Study

Appendix 2

Year wise financial data of BPCL from 2008-09 to 2018-19

Year	PAT	Net Sales	PBIT	Net Worth	Long Term Capital Employed	Total Expenses	Total Income	Net Fixed Assets
2008-09	735.90	135237.70	3170.48	12128.11	34538.76	134152.99	135170.56	14003.27
2009-10	1537.62	122275.95	3377.00	13086.71	36141.21	126084.56	128506.04	16187.10
2010-11	1546.68	151545.06	3513.43	14057.62	34037.03	152933.34	155356.08	17011.56
2011-12	1311.27	211972.97	3683.76	14913.86	18939.43	211790.58	213674.75	17731.44
2012-13	2642.90	240115.75	5860.93	16634.02	24293.99	237760.29	241795.98	19110.15
2013-14	4060.88	260060.53	7308.06	19458.76	33846.07	255580.21	261529.19	22104.61
2014-15	5084.51	238086.90	7998.61	22467.48	37091.38	232871.35	240286.86	27980.74
2015-16	7431.88	189303.30	11214.12	27158.69	44290.85	180664.31	191315.49	36085.72
2016-17	8039.30	242047.82	11538.66	29668.38	48444.84	233605.71	244648.50	44671.21
2017-18	7919.34	277162.23	12031.26	34152.00	55430.43	268975.10	280173.11	49361.70
2018-19	7132.02	337622.53	11758.58	36737.68	68385.59	330166.51	340606.13	55513.10

Source: BPCL Annual Report from 2009-10 to 2018-19

Appendix2: Year wise financial data of BPCL from 2008-09 to 2018-19 (All the amount in ₹crores)

Appendix 3

Estimation for Next Three Years with Regression Model Without Intercept

Year	Ratios	If BPCL will not be privatised	If BPCL will be privatised
2019-20	PAT	9,742.63	7,161.33
	Net Sales	3,02,433.22	2,77,681.59
	PBIT	13,912.05	11,705.73
	Net Worth	36,789.71	36,084.58
	Long Term Capital Employed	54,865.27	59,735.71
	Total Expenses	2,92,232.33	2,67,495.35
	Total Income	3,05,170.69	2,81,128.36
	Net Fixed Assets	56,222.49	45,558.72
2020-21	PAT	10,804.85	7,443.35
	Net Sales	3,12,923.65	2,83,028.88
	PBIT	15,006.35	12,194.86
	Net Worth	39,086.39	38,187.67
	Long Term Capital Employed	56,730.48	62,762.58
	Total Expenses	3,01,762.32	2,71,996.68
	Total Income	3,15,692.26	2,86,649.98
	Net Fixed Assets	61,016.95	47,377.52
2021-22	PAT	11,898.73	7,715.52
	Net Sales	3,23,002.64	2,88,089.83
	PBIT	16,102.42	12,668.03
	Net Worth	41,352.16	40,254.35
	Long Term Capital Employed	58,521.33	65,715.66
	Total Expenses	3,10,900.18	2,76,246.83
	Total Income	3,25,799.15	2,91,877.90
	Net Fixed Assets	65,848.61	49,133.82

Source: Author's Calculation

Appendix3: Estimation for next three years with regression model without intercept (All the amount in ₹crores)

Appendix 4

Estimation for Next Three Years with Regression Model with Intercept

Year	Ratios	If BPCL will not be privatised	If BPCL will be privatised
2019-20	PAT	9394.89	11109.39
	Net Sales	299632.15	130191.95
	PBIT	14343.99	16265.20
	Net Worth	42804.07	49,753.7107
	Long Term Capital Employed	64561.07	103833.30
	Total Expenses	288003.96	116366.43
	Total Income	302713.12	131976.87
	Net Fixed Assets	68073.25	66888.93
2020-21	PAT	10273.32	12645.78
	Net Sales	309175.67	121449.33
	PBIT	15644.36	18278.42
	Net Worth	48193.71	58,358.6381
	Long Term Capital Employed	70838.23	130590.77
	Total Expenses	296145.42	108364.12
	Total Income	312401.63	123056.84
	Net Fixed Assets	79849.91	78073.65
2021-22	PAT	11157.53	14258.28
	Net Sales	318274.66	113971.43
	PBIT	16971.64	20393.34
	Net Worth	54050.02	68,035.0943
	Long Term Capital Employed	77634.60	162902.23
	Total Expenses	303855.11	101599.96
	Total Income	321645.92	115418.51
	Net Fixed Assets	93139.95	90643.39

Source: Author's Calculation

Appendix4: Estimation for next three years with regression model with intercept (All the amount in ₹crores)

Appendix 5**Dividend History of BPCL (Final Dividend)**

Announcement Date	Dividend(%)
20/05/2019	80%
29/05/2018	70%
30/05/2017	10%
26/05/2016	150%
28/05/2015	225%
29/05/2014	170%
29/05/2013	110%
25/05/2012	110%
30/05/2011	140%
27/05/2010	140%
29/05/2009	70%
17/06/2008	40%
24/05/2007	100%
27/09/2006	25%
20/05/2004	115%
30/05/2003	130%
27/06/2002	110%
06/03/2001	35%
28/06/2000	125%
30/07/1999	125%
25/05/1998	50%
29/05/1997	33%

Source: Economic Times Website

Appendix5: Dividend History of BPCL (Final Dividend)

Appendix 6

Dividend History of BPCL (Interim Dividend)

Announcement Date	Dividend(%)
12/03/2020	165%
08/02/2019	110%
09/02/2018	140%
23/03/2017	120%
10/02/2017	195%
12/02/2016	35%
20/01/2016	125%

Source: Economic Times Website

Appendix6: Dividend History of BPCL (Interim Dividend)

Appendix 7

Bonus History of BPCL

Announcement Date	Bonus Ratio
30/05/2017	1 : 2
26/05/2016	1 : 1
25/05/2012	1 : 1
28/09/2000	1 : 1
02/09/1994	2 : 1

Source: Economic Times Website

Appendix7: Bonus History of BPCL

Appendix 8

Public Offer: Initial Sale of Minority Shareholding

SL. NO.	COMPANY (NAME AS AT THE TIME OF DISINVESTMENT)	FY	% STAKE DISINVESTED	AMOUNT REALISED (Rs. crore)
1	BHARAT DYNAMICS LTD.	2017-18	12.25	952.25
2	COAL INDIA LTD.	2010-11	10	15199.44
3	COCHIN SHIPYARD LTD.	2017-18	8.33	480.98
4	GARDEN REACH SHIPBUILDERS & ENGINEERS LTD.	2018-19	25.5	343.59
5	GENERAL INSURANCE CORP.OF INDIA	2017-18	12.25	9704.16
6	HINDUSTAN AERONAUTICS LTD.	2017-18	10.03	4063.31
7	HOUSING & URBAN DEVELOPMENT CORP.LTD.	2017-18	10.19	1209.78
8	INDIAN RAILWAY CATERING & TOURISM CORP.LTD.	2019-20	12.6	637.97
9	IRCON INTERNATIONAL LTD.	2018-19	10.53	466.93
10	MISHRA DHATU NIGAM LTD.	2017-18	26	432.9
11	MOIL LTD.	2010-11	20	1237.51
12	MSTC LTD.	2018-19	25.1	211.04
13	NATIONAL BUILDINGS CONSTRUCTION CORP.LTD.	2011-12	10	124.97
14	NATIONAL THERMAL POWER CORP.LTD.	2004-05	5.25	2684.07
15	NEW INDIA ASSURANCE CO.LTD.,THE	2017-18	11.65	7668.66
16	NHPC LTD.	2009-10	4.55	2012.85
17	POWER GRID CORP.OF INDIA LTD.	2007-08	4.55	994.82
18	RAIL VIKAS NIGAM LTD.	2018-19	12.16	476.86
19	BITES LTD.	2018-19	12.6	460.51
20	RURAL ELECTRIFICATION CORP.LTD.	2007-08	9.09	819.63
21	SJVN LTD.	2010-11	10.03	1062.51

Source: BSE PSU Website

Appendix8: Public Offer: Initial Sale of Minority Shareholding

Appendix 9**Public Offer: Subsequent Sale of Minority Shareholding**

SL. NO.	COMPANY (NAME AS AT THE TIME OF DISINVESTMENT)	FY	% STAKE DISINVESTED	AMOUNT REALISED (Rs. crore)
1	DREDGING CORP.OF INDIA LTD.	2003-04	20	221.2
2	DREDGING CORP.OF INDIA LTD.	2015-16	5	53.64
3	ENGINEERS INDIA LTD.	2010-11	10	959.65
4	ENGINEERS INDIA LTD.	2013-14	10	497.32
5	GAIL (INDIA) LTD. (GDR)	1999-00	15.98	945
6	GAIL (INDIA) LTD.	2003-04	10	1627.36
7	INDIAN OIL CORP.LTD.	2015-16	10	9396.18
8	MAHANAGAR TELEPHONE NIGAM LTD. (GDR)	1997-98	7.13	910
9	NMDC LTD.	2009-10	8.38	9930.45
10	NTPC LTD.	2009-10	5	8480.1
11	OIL & NATURAL GAS CORP.LTD.	2003-04	9.96	10542.4
12	OIL & NATURAL GAS CORP.LTD. (SPILLOVER)	2004-05		15.99
13	POWER FINANCE CORP.LTD.	2011-12	4.35	1144.55
14	POWER FINANCE CORP.LTD.	2015-16	5	1671.76
15	POWER GRID CORP.OF INDIA LTD.	2010-11	9.09	3721.17
16	POWER GRID CORP.OF INDIA LTD.	2013-14	3.54	1637.33
17	RURAL ELECTRIFICATION CORP.LTD.	2009-10	4.35	882.51
18	SHIPPING CORP.OF INDIA LTD.,THE	2010-11	9.09	582.45
19	VIDESH SANCHAR NIGAM LTD. (GDR)	1996-97	2.94	379.67
20	VIDESH SANCHAR NIGAM LTD. (GDR)	1998-99	7.54	783.68
21	VIDESH SANCHAR NIGAM LTD.	1999-00	1.05	75

Source: BSE PSU Website

Appendix9: Public Offer: Subsequent Sale of Minority Shareholding

Appendix 10

Public Offer: Offer for Sale of Shares by Promoters through Stock Exchange Mechanism

SL. NO.	COMPANY (NAME AS AT THE TIME OF DISINVESTMENT)	FY	% STAKE DISINVESTED	AMOUNT REALISED (Rs. crore)
1	AXIS BANK LTD.(SPECIFIED UNDERTAKING OF THE UNIT TRUST OF INDIA)	2018-19	9.29	5358.25
2	BHARAT ELECTRONICS LTD.	2016-17	5	1687.2
3	COAL INDIA LTD.	2014-15	10	22557.62
4	COAL INDIA LTD.	2018-19	5.19	5273.72
5	CONTAINER CORP.OF INDIA LTD.	2015-16	5	1165.96
6	ENGINEERS INDIA LTD.	2015-16	10	645.27
7	HINDUSTAN COPPER LTD.	2012-13	5.58	807.91
8	HINDUSTAN COPPER LTD.	2013-14	4.01	259.84
9	HINDUSTAN COPPER LTD.	2016-17	7	401.54
10	HINDUSTAN COPPER LTD.	2017-18	6.83	409.04
11	INDIA TOURISM DEVELOPMENT CORP.LTD.	2013-14	5	30.17
12	MMTC LTD.	2013-14	9.33	572.34
13	MOIL LTD.	2016-17	10	489.48
14	NATIONAL ALUMINIUM CO.LTD.	2012-13	6.09	628.53
15	NATIONAL ALUMINIUM CO.LTD.	2017-18	9.22	1203.04
16	NATIONAL FERTILIZERS LTD.	2013-14	7.64	101.08
17	NATIONAL FERTILIZERS LTD.	2017-18	15	536.11
18	NBCC (INDIA) LTD.	2016-17	15	2218.5
19	NHPC LTD.	2016-17	11.36	2735.34
20	NLC INDIA LTD.	2017-18	5	724.85
21	NMDC LTD.	2012-13	10	5979.79
22	NMDC LTD.	2017-18	2.51	1233.18
23	NTPC LTD.	2012-13	9.5	11469.39
24	NTPC LTD.	2015-16	5	5031.61
25	NTPC LTD.	2017-18	6.63	9192.13
26	OIL & NATURAL GAS CORP.LTD.	2011-12	4.91	12765.75
27	OIL INDIA LTD.	2012-13	10	3144.97
28	RASHTRIYA CHEMICALS & FERTILISERS LTD.	2012-13	12.5	310.49
29	RASHTRIYA CHEMICALS & FERTILIZERS LTD.	2017-18	5	207.19
30	RITES LTD.	2019-20	10	733.83
31	RITES LTD.	2019-20	5.37	399.69
32	RURAL ELECTRIFICATION CORP.LTD.	2015-16	5	1610.09
33	STATE TRADING CORP.OF INDIA LTD.,THE	2013-14	1.02	4.54
34	STEEL AUTHORITY OF INDIA LTD.	2012-13	5.82	1516.17
35	STEEL AUTHORITY OF INDIA LTD.	2014-15	5	1719.54

Source: BSE PSU Website

Appendix10: Public Offer: Offer for Sale of Shares by Promoters through Stock Exchange Mechanism

Appendix 11**Public Offer: Other Sale of Minority Shareholding**

SL. NO.	COMPANY (NAME AS AT THE TIME OF DISINVESTMENT)	FY	% STAKE DISINVESTED	AMOUNT REALISED (Rs. crore)
1	INDIAN PETROCHEMICALS CORP.LTD.	2003-04	28.95	1202.85
2	MARUTI UDYOG LTD.	2003-04	27.51	993.34

Source: BSE PSU Website

Appendix11: Public Offer: Other Sale of Minority Shareholding

Appendix 12

Public Offer: Sale of Residual Shareholding

SL. NO.	COMPANY (NAME AS AT THE TIME OF DISINVESTMENT)	FY	% STAKE DISINVESTED	AMOUNT REALISED (Rs. crore)
1	CMC LTD.	2003-04	26.25	190.44
2	IBP CO.LTD.	2003-04	26	350.66

Source: BSE PSU Website

Appendix12: Public Offer: Sale of Residual Shareholding

Appendix 13**Strategic Sale to Private Entity: Initial Sale of Complete Shareholding**

SL. NO.	COMPANY (NAME AS AT THE TIME OF DISINVESTMENT)	FY	NAME OF BUYER, IF ANY	% STAKE DISINVESTED	AMOUNT REALISED (Rs. crore)
1	HOTEL CORP.OF INDIA LTD. - INDO HOKKE HOTELS LTD.RAJGIR	2001-02	INPAC TRAVELS (INDIA) PVT.LTD.	100	6.51
2	INDIA TOURISM DEVELOPMENT CORP.LTD. - HOTEL HASSAN ASHOK	2001-02	MALNAD HOTELS& RESORTS PVT.LTD.	89.97	2.27
3	INDIA TOURISM DEVELOPMENT CORP.LTD. - HOTEL BODHGAYA ASHOK	2001-02	LOTUS NIKKO HOTELS	89.97	1.81
4	INDIA TOURISM DEVELOPMENT CORP.LTD. - HOTEL MADURAI ASHOK	2001-02	SANGU CHAKRA HOTELS PVT.LTD.	89.97	4.98
5	INDIA TOURISM DEVELOPMENT CORP.LTD. - TEMPLE BAY ASHOK BEACH RESORT, MAMALLAPURAM	2001-02	G.R.THANGA MALIGAI PVT.LTD.	89.97	6.13
6	INDIA TOURISM DEVELOPMENT CORP.LTD. - HOTEL AGRA ASHOK	2001-02	MOHAN SINGH	89.97	3.61
7	INDIA TOURISM DEVELOPMENT CORP.LTD. - LAXMI VILAS PALACE HOTEL, UDAIPUR	2001-02	BHARAT HOTELS LTD.	89.97	6.77
8	INDIA TOURISM DEVELOPMENT CORP.LTD. - QUTAB HOTEL, NEW DELHI	2001-02	CONSORTIUM OF SUSHIL GUPTA & OTHERS	89.97	34.45
9	INDIA TOURISM DEVELOPMENT CORP.LTD. - LODHI HOTEL, NEW DELHI	2001-02	SILVERLINK HOLDINGS LTD.& CONSORTIUM	89.97	71.93
10	INDIA TOURISM DEVELOPMENT CORP.LTD. - HOTEL AIRPORT ASHOK, KOLKATA	2002-03	BRIGHT ENTERPRISES PVT.LTD.& CONSORTIUM	89.97	19.39
11	INDIA TOURISM DEVELOPMENT CORP.LTD. - KOVALAM ASHOK BEACH RESORT	2002-03	M FAR HOTELS LTD.	89.97	40.38
12	INDIA TOURISM DEVELOPMENT CORP.LTD. - HOTEL AURANGABAD ASHOK	2002-03	LOKSANGAM HOTELS & RESORTS PVT.LTD.& CONSORTIUM	89.97	16.5
13	INDIA TOURISM DEVELOPMENT CORP.LTD. - HOTEL MANALI ASHOK	2002-03	AUTO IMPEX LTD.	89.97	3.66
14	INDIA TOURISM DEVELOPMENT CORP.LTD. - HOTEL KHAJURAO ASHOK	2002-03	BHARAT HOTELS LTD.	89.97	2.19
15	INDIA TOURISM DEVELOPMENT CORP.LTD. - HOTEL RANJIT, NEW DELHI	2002-03	CONSORTIUM OF UNISON HOTELS LTD.& FORMAX COMMERCIAL PVT.LTD.	89.97	29.28
16	INDIA TOURISM DEVELOPMENT CORP.LTD. - HOTEL KANISHKA, NEW DELHI	2002-03	NEHRU PLACE HOTELS LTD.	89.97	92.38
17	INDIA TOURISM DEVELOPMENT CORP.LTD. - HOTEL INDRAPRASTHA, NEW DELHI	2002-03	MORAL TRADING & INVESTMENT LTD.	89.97	43.38
18	INDIA TOURISM DEVELOPMENT CORP.LTD. - PUNJAB HOTEL LTD.	2002-03	TAJGVK HOTELS & RESORTS LTD.	100	17.27
19	INDIA TOURISM DEVELOPMENT CORP.LTD. - HOTEL VARANASI ASHOK	2002-03	CONSORTIUM OF RAMNATH HOTELS PVT.LTD.	89.97	8.38

Source: BSE PSU Website

Appendix13: Strategic Sale to Private Entity: Initial Sale of Complete Shareholding

Appendix 14

Strategic Sale to Private Entity: Slump Sale

SL. NO.	COMPANY (NAME AS AT THE TIME OF DISINVESTMENT)	FY	NAME OF BUYER, IF ANY	% STAKE DISINVESTED	AMOUNT REALISED (Rs. crore)
1	HOTEL CORP.OF INDIA LTD. - CENTAUR HOTEL JUHU BEACH, MUMBAI	2001-02	TULIP HOSPITALITY PVT.LTD.	100	153
2	HOTEL CORP.OF INDIA LTD. - CENTAUR HOTEL AIRPORT, MUMBAI	2002-03	BATRA HOSPITALITY PVT.LTD.	100	83

Source: BSE PSU Website

Appendix14: Strategic Sale to Private Entity: Slump Sale

Appendix 15**Strategic Sale to Private Entity: Initial Sale of Majority Shareholding**

SL. NO.	COMPANY (NAME AS AT THE TIME OF DISINVESTMENT)	FY	NAME OF BUYER, IF ANY	% STAKE DISINVESTED	AMOUNT REALISED (Rs. crore)
1	BHARAT ALUMINIUM CO.LTD.	2000-01	STERLITE INDUSTRIES (INDIA) LTD.	51	551.5
2	CMC LTD.	2001-02	TATA CONSULTANCY SERVICES LTD.	51	152
3	HINDUSTAN TELEPRINTERS LTD.	2001-02	HIMACHAL FUTURISTIC COMMUNICATION LTD.	74	55
4	HINDUSTAN ZINC LTD.	2002-03	STERLITE OPPORTUNITIES & VENTURES LTD.	22.07	445
5	INDIAN PETROCHEMICALS CORP.LTD.	2002-03	RELIANCE PETRO INVESTMENTS LTD.	26	1490.84
6	JESSOP & CO.LTD.	2003-04	INDO WAGON ENGINEERING LTD.	72	18.18
7	LAGAN JUTE MACHINERY CO.LTD.,THE	2000-01	MURALIDHAR RATANLAL EXPORTS LTD.	74	2.53
8	MODERN FOOD INDUSTRIES (INDIA) LTD.	1999-00	HINDUSTAN LEVER LTD.	74	105.45
9	PARADEEP PHOSPHATES LTD.	2001-02	ZUARI MAROC PHOSPHATES PVT.LTD.	74	151.7
10	VIDESH SANCHAR NIGAM LTD.	2001-02	PANATONE FINVEST LTD.(A TATA GROUP CO.)	25	1439.25

Source: BSE PSU Website

Appendix 15: Strategic Sale to Private Entity: Initial Sale of Majority Shareholding

Appendix 16

Strategic Sale to Private Entity: Subsequent Sale of Minority Shareholding leading to Further Dilution

SL. NO.	COMPANY (NAME AS AT THE TIME OF DISINVESTMENT)	FY	NAME OF BUYER, IF ANY	% STAKE DISINVESTED	AMOUNT REALISED (Rs. crore)
1	HINDUSTAN ZINC LTD. (CALL OPTION)	2003-04	STERLITE OPPORTUNITIES & VENTURES LTD.	18.92	323.88

Source: BSE PSU Website

Appendix 16: Strategic Sale to Private Entity: Subsequent Sale of Minority Shareholding leading to Further Dilution

Appendix 17

Strategic Sale to Private Entity: Subsequent Sale of Minority Shareholding leading to Complete Privatisation

SL. NO.	COMPANY (NAME AS AT THE TIME OF DISINVESTMENT)	FY	NAME OF BUYER, IF ANY	% STAKE DISINVESTED	AMOUNT REALISED (Rs. crore)
1	MODERN FOOD INDUSTRIES (INDIA) LTD. (PUT OPTION)	2002-03	HINDUSTAN LEVER LTD.	26	44.07

Source: BSE PSU Website

Appendix 17: Strategic Sale to Private Entity: Subsequent Sale of Minority Shareholding leading to Complete Privatisation

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Annexure I Valuation Methodology in Strategic Sale²

In any sale process, the sale will materialise only when the seller is satisfied that the price given by the buyer is not less than the value of the object being sold. Determination of that threshold amount, which the seller considers adequate, therefore, is the first pre-requisite for conducting any sale. This threshold amount is called the 'Reserve Price' (See definition 10 Reserve Price). In companies which are listed on the Stock Exchanges, market price of the shares serves as a good benchmark for assessing the fair value of the company, though the market price is usually characterised with significant short-term variance due to investor sentiments being influenced by short-term events and environmental aspects. More importantly, most of the PSUs are either not listed on the Stock Exchanges or command extremely limited traded float. They are, therefore, not correctly valued. Thus, deciding the worth of a PSU is indeed a challenging task.

Another point worth mentioning is that valuation of a PSU is different from establishing the price for which it can be sold. Experts are of the opinion that valuation must be differentiated from price. While the fair value of an asset is based on the assessment of intrinsic value accruing from fundamentals on a stand-alone basis, varying return expectation and underlying strategic aspects for different bidders could influence the price. A purchase and sale would be possible only when two parties while forming different views as to the value of an asset, are eventually able to reach agreement on the same price. It would be better appreciated by recognition of the fact that Government can only realise what a buyer is willing to pay for the PSU, as the purchase price ultimately agreed reflects its value to the buyer.

²Excerpted from the document titled 'Valuation Methodology' released by Department of Investment and Public Asset Management, Ministry of Finance, Government of India.

Another notable point is that valuation is a subjective figure arrived at by the bidder by leveraging his strengths with the potential of the company. Depending on the level of business synergy with the target company, perception of specific value realisation and varying assessment regarding productivity, capex, etc., this figure may vary from bidder to bidder.

Based on the recommendations of the Disinvestment Commission and in keeping with the best market practices the following four methodologies are being used for valuation of PSUs:

1. Discounted Cash Flow (DCF) Method.
2. Balance Sheet Method.
3. Transaction Multiple Method.
4. Asset Valuation Method.

While the first three are business valuation methodologies generally used for valuation of a going concern, the last methodology would be relevant only for valuation of assets in case of liquidation of a company. In addition, in case of listed companies, the market value of shares during the last six months is also used as an indicator. However, most PSU stocks suffer from low liquidity and the price determination may not be always efficient. Moreover, there could be increased trading activity after announcement of the disinvestment, which could be on account of high market expectation of the bid price and even based on malafide intent. This could lead to the price being traded up to unsustainable levels, which is not desirable.

Discounted Cash Flow (DCF) method

The Discounted Cash Flow (DCF) methodology expresses the present value of a business as a function of its future cash earnings capacity. This methodology works on the premise that the value of a business is measured in terms of future cash flow streams, discounted to the present time at an appropriate discount rate.

This method is used to determine the present value of a business on a going concern assumption. It recognises that money has a time value by discounting future cash flows at an appropriate discount factor. The DCF methodology depends on the projection of the future cash flows and the selection of an appropriate discount factor.

When valuing a business on a DCF basis, the objective is to determine a net present value of

the free cash flows ('FCF') (See definition 11 Free Cash Flow) arising from the business over a future period of time (say 5 years), which period is called the explicit forecast period. Under the DCF methodology, value must be placed both on the explicit cash flows as stated above, and the ongoing cash flows a company will generate after the explicit forecast period. The latter value, also known as terminal value, is also to be estimated.

The further the cash flows can be projected, the less sensitive the valuation is to inaccuracies in the assumed terminal value. Therefore, the longer the period covered by the projection, the less reliable the projections are likely to be. For this reason, the approach is used to value businesses, where the future cash flows can be projected with a reasonable degree of reliability. For example, in a fast changing market like telecom or even automobile, the explicit period typically cannot be more than at least 5 years. Any projection beyond that would be mostly speculation.

The discount rate applied to estimate the present value of explicit forecast period free cash flows as also continuing value, is taken at the 'Weighted Average Cost of Capital' (WACC). One of the advantages of the DCF approach is that it permits the various elements that make up the discount factor to be considered separately, and thus, the effect of the variations in the assumptions can be modelled more easily. The principal elements of WACC are cost of equity (which is the desired rate of return for an equity investor given the risk profile of the company and associated cash flows), the post-tax cost of debt and the target capital structure of the company (a function of debt to equity ratio). In turn, cost of equity is derived, on the basis of capital asset pricing model (CAPM), as a function of risk-free rate, Beta (an estimate of risk profile of the company relative to equity market) and equity risk premium assigned to the subject equity market.

The DCF methodology is the most appropriate methodology in the following cases:

- Where the business is being transferred / acquired on a going concern basis;
- Where the business possesses substantial intangibles like brand, goodwill, marketing and distribution network, etc;
- Where the business is not being valued for the substantial undisclosed assets it possesses.

The DCF methodology is considered to be the best methodology for valuation the world over because it takes into account all the factors relevant for valuation. It takes into consideration all

the cash flows available to stakeholders of a firm and the necessary outflows, as estimated for the future. Further, the net present value takes into account the cost of debt, cost of equity and target capital structure. It also takes into account the risks to which the enterprise is exposed. The discount rate (i.e. the average expected return on capital employed) is based on the overall risk perception of the business. It also takes into account the value of the non-core assets of the company. Any business has two kinds of assets - core assets that are a part of the business and non-core assets that are not directly utilised as part of core operations and hence can be treated as surplus assets. The asset value of core assets is reflected in the cash flows of the company and, therefore, should not be added separately to it. However non-core assets are not reflected in the cash flows. Therefore, asset valuation of non-core assets should be done separately and should be added to DCF valuation.

Being fundamentally driven by future business plan of the company and associated cash flows, a prudent DCF valuation should be able to capture the capital costs for renovation and modernisation of plant and machinery. The age and condition of assets like plant and machinery and their replacement value would be relevant for estimating expenditure on their replacement whenever necessary. This expenditure will reduce cash flows and DCF value. Valuation of plant and machinery would be a relevant item that would influence the DCF valuation. For example, a person acquiring a company operating a fleet of taxis would examine the conditions of vehicles for valuation of the company. If the vehicles need replacement of a low cost item like hub caps, the impact on DCF will be less than if they need to replace gear boxes in a high proportion of vehicles. The person would also calculate DCF with reference to the demand for taxis, the average mileage, cost of maintenance etc. Valuation of plant and machinery is not a simple addition to DCF, but a factor to be taken into account while calculating DCF. In such calculation, plant and machinery may be a net negative factor in the DCF if replacement costs are high. Where surplus land would be sold this would be a positive factor. If the sale of land can cover the cost of plant replacement the net effect would be neutral on DCF.

For a going concern, various intangibles like brand equity, market share, competition, etc have a significant bearing on the valuation of the company. One cannot place a money value for these factors. They have no financial value of their own that can be measured in money terms. Hence, there is no way of evaluating them in any other methodology. DCF is the only methodology, which takes into account these factors by incorporating them intrinsically in estimated cash flows. In calculating DCF, different assumptions will be made of market share, compe-

tion from imports etc, which are translated into financial terms. Sensitivity analysis can also be made for different assumptions. The Financial Advisor and the Seller should exercise the judgement on the most likely financial impact of the intangible assets the company possesses, on cash flows and also on the discount rate to be applied while arriving at the optimum DCF value, as strong intangible assets would help reduce the overall risk perception of the company.

In a strategic sale, the bidders take into account not only DCF valuation, but also a premium for management control. Premium for management control would be a subjective item for each bidder and will be reflected in the competitive bids. Therefore, the seller, while calculating the Reserve Price, should not incorporate this premium in the valuation amount separately. Since there is no scientific method to quantify the control premium, it may be arbitrary to add control premium while arriving at the Reserve Price.

Balance Sheet method

The Balance sheet or the Net Asset Value (NAV) methodology values a business on the basis of the value of its underlying assets. This is relevant where the value of the business is fairly represented by its underlying assets. The NAV method is normally used to determine the minimum price a seller would be willing to accept and, thus serves to establish the floor for the value of the business. This method is pertinent where:

- The value of intangibles is not significant;
- The business has been recently set up.

This method takes into account the net value of the assets of a business or the capital employed as represented in the financial statements. Hence, this method takes into account the amount that is historically spent and earned from the business. This method does not, however, consider the earnings potential of the assets and is, therefore, seldom used for valuing a going concern. The above method is not considered appropriate, particularly in the following cases:

- When the financial statement sheets do not reflect the true value of assets, being either too high on account of possible losses not reflected in the balance sheet or too low because of initial losses which may not continue in future;
- Where intangibles such as brand, goodwill, marketing infrastructure, and product devel-

opment capabilities, etc., form a major part of the value of the company;

- Where due to the changes in industry, market or business environment, the assets of the company have become redundant and their ability to create net positive cash flows in future is limited.

Market Multiple Method

This method takes into account the traded or transaction value of comparable companies in the industry and benchmarks it against certain parameters, like earnings, sales, etc. Two of such commonly used parameters are:

- Earnings before Interest, Taxes, Depreciation & Amortisations (EBITDA)
- Sales

Although the Market Multiples method captures most value elements of a business, it is based on the past/current transaction or traded values and does not reflect the possible changes in future of the trend of cash flows being generated by a business, neither takes into account the time value of money adequately. At the same time it is a reflection of the current view of the market and hence is considered as a useful rule of thumb, providing reasonableness checks to valuations arrived at from other approaches. Accordingly, one may have to review a series of comparable transactions to determine a range of appropriate capitalisation factors to value a company as per this methodology.

EBITDA multiple

The EBITDA multiple or the earnings method is based on the premise that the value of a business is directly related to the quantum of its gross profits. The net profits are adjusted to reflect the operating recurring profits of the business on a standalone basis (i.e. after deducting extraordinary or unusual items, or items of a non-recurring nature). Further, the profits are adjusted for non-cash items (including depreciation and amortisation) and other factors, such as interest and taxation (which vary from business to business) to derive EBITDA (Earnings Before Interest, Taxation, Depreciation and Amortisations).

The EBITDA multiple method takes into account the value or consideration paid by ac-

quirers of similar businesses, and is computed by dividing the total consideration paid (after adjusting for any debt assumed) by the EBITDA to derive a multiple, which can be applied to the EBITDA figure of the business being valued. i.e. adjusted maintainable EBITDA are capitalised by an appropriate factor ("capitalisation factor") to arrive at the business value.

$$EBITDA\text{multiple} = \frac{\text{Enterprise Value}}{EBITDA} \quad (1)$$

Where:

Enterprise Value (EV) = Market value of Equity + Market value of Debt

EBITDA = Earnings Before Interest, Tax, Depreciation and Amortization

To illustrate, if we are valuing Company X with EBITDA of Rs. 150 million and in a similar transaction EBITDA multiple has been 10 then EV of Company X would be worked out as Rs. 1500 million and then debt would be deducted to arrive at the equity value of Company X.

Sales multiple

The sales multiple techniques are based on a similar analysis of relevant acquisitions and are the ratio of Enterprise Value to the current sales (net of excise duty, sales tax and non-recurring extra-ordinary income). It is calculated as follows:

$$\text{Sales multiple} = \frac{\text{Enterprises Value}}{\text{Net sales of the current year}} \quad (2)$$

To illustrate, if we are valuing Company X with sales of Rs. 500 million and in a similar transaction EV/Sales has been 4 (Sales multiple) then EV of Company X would be worked out as Rs. 2000 million. Then debt would be deducted to arrive at the equity value of Company X.

The Transaction Multiple methodology suffers from the following drawbacks:

- Actual money required to earn the maintainable profits / sales of the business as a going concern (for instance, future capital expenditure) are not considered.
- This methodology does not take into account the time value of money.

Notwithstanding these limitations, these multiples are widely used by investors to arrive at benchmark values for a company.

Asset Valuation Methodology

The asset valuation methodology essentially estimates the cost of replacing the tangible assets of the business. The replacement cost takes into account the market value of various assets or the expenditure required to create the infrastructure exactly similar to that of a company being valued. Since the replacement methodology assumes the value of business as if we were setting a new business, this methodology may not be relevant in a going concern. Instead it will be more realistic if asset valuation is done on the basis of the new book value of the assets. The asset valuation is a good indicator of the entry barrier that exists in a business. Alternatively, this methodology can also assume the amount which can be realised by liquidating the business by selling off all the tangible assets of a company and paying off the liabilities.

The asset valuation methodology is useful in case of liquidation/closure of the business. In this case certain adjustments may have to be made to the equity value arrived at by this method including settlement of all borrowings on the company's balance sheet on the date of valuation and settlement of employee dues. These adjustments should include all the process related cost involved in closure and liquidation.

In a strategic sale process, however, the proposal is normally to transfer management control of a going concern to a strategic partner. These concerns may contain surplus assets as land and building which may not form part of the core assets required for operations and hence their fair value may not be captured if the valuation of subject entity is based on DCF or Market Multiples approaches. To protect this, certain restrictions are imposed on the strategic partner on usage and disposal of such surplus assets e.g. the land and property of the business cannot be sold or put to alternate use by the strategic partner. However, certain economic benefits from such assets would still accrue to an extent to the strategic partner as the owner of majority interest in the company. Accordingly, while the asset valuation method may not provide the best estimate of the value of the enterprise, application of this approach to surplus assets would help provide a better assessment of the Reserve Price. In practice, it has been used so far for valuing the CPSEs under disinvestment because the Disinvestment Commission had recommended that this method should also be followed for valuation in the case of strategic sale.

The Asset Valuation approach suffers from certain very serious limitations. These are detailed below:

1. Practically, it is extremely difficult to determine the exact replacement cost of the assets owned by a company. This is so on account of number of reasons, such as
 - (a) Changes in technology over a period of time (resulting in certain assets not being produced at all or being produced with far more efficiencies than earlier)
 - (b) Absence of a marketplace where such assets are or can be traded
 - (c) inability of the seller to be able to actually realise the value of assets in one go should the company be liquidated
 - (d) changes in the duty structure (like excise, import duties, etc which may impact the value of the asset over different periods of time) etc.
2. The Asset Valuation approach also does not take into account the very purpose for which a company acquired the assets, i.e., for future economic benefits. Hence, the historical or replacement cost of a particular asset may tend to convey a wrong picture of the value that the buyer may perceive in the asset. These factors often tend to result in a higher value being attributed to the assets and the companies, if the asset valuation approach is followed. Assets are bought and sold for their future economic benefits, and for established and running businesses; the economic benefits of owning the assets are far more relevant than the historical cost or replacement cost of the assets.
3. The Asset Valuation approach also tends to overlook the intangible assets that a company, over a period of its existence tends to build, such as goodwill, brands, distribution network, customer relationships, etc, all of which are very important to determine its true intrinsic value.
4. In the case of a majority of the PSUs it may be found that the replacement cost or liquidation value is higher than the intrinsic value of the company, if determined on the basis of the company's future profitability (cash flows). As against this, a company, which has been generating very healthy returns and has built strong brand equity, goodwill etc., will tend to command a value that is far higher than the value of its tangible assets.

Annexure II Detailed Procedure of BPCL Disinvestment³

The following activities shall be carried out post submission of EoI as part of the process:

1. Shortlisting of Qualified Interested Parties (QIP) – EoIs submitted by IPs shall be evaluated as per the criteria provided in the PIM. The decision regarding shortlisting shall be communicated to the IPs.
2. Issuance of RFP and SPA – The RFP and SPA shall be shared with QIPs via the Data Room (DR).
3. Access to DR and Due-diligence – The QIPs may carry out due-diligence based on information shared in the DR. Any queries or requests for further information shall be entertained depending on the nature of information requested.
4. Submission of Financial Bids – The QIPs shall be required to undergo a bidding process in accordance with the terms of the RFP.
5. Security Clearance – Necessary security clearance, if required, shall be taken as per extant instructions of the Government of India. Each QIP will need to apply for security clearance at the time of submission of Financial Bids.
6. Setting up of Reserve Price – The GoI shall set up the reserve price for the transaction after the receipt of the bids, but prior to opening of the bids. The reserve price shall be confidential and shall not be known to bidders.

³Excerpted from the document titled 'Preliminary Information Memorandum: For Inviting Expression of Interest For Strategic Disinvestment of Bharat Petroleum Corporation Limited (BPCL)' released by Department of Investment and Public Asset Management, Ministry of Finance, Government of India.

7. Bid Evaluation and Government Approval – GoI shall evaluate the bids and approve the H1 bidder (highest bidder). The H1 bidder post receipt of security clearance, if any, shall be called the Confirmed Selected Bidder (CSB).
8. Execution of SPA – A Share Purchase Agreement (SPA) shall be executed with the CSB.
9. Approvals of statutory authorities – All requisite approvals from statutory/regulatory authorities to be obtained by the CSB.
10. Open Offer – CSB is required to make an Open Offer to public shareholders to acquire minimum 26% shares of BPCL. The CSB will not be allowed to make the open offer conditional on any minimum level of acceptance. The CSB will be required to put in escrow in cash the entire consideration payable under the open offer assuming full acceptance of the open offer.
11. Payment of Consideration and Transfer of Shares – The details relating to payment of consideration and transfer of shares will be mentioned in the RFP.

Annexure III Eligibility Criteria⁴

This section deals with eligibility criteria for IP and the primary eligibility criteria are as follows:

1. Any private limited company or public limited company registered under Companies Act 1956 or 2013, Limited Liability Partnership (LLP) or SEBI registered Alternative Investment Fund (AIF), or a company/ a fund incorporated outside India, which is eligible to invest in India under the laws of India (subject to such parties obtaining all statutory approvals from GoI/FIFP/RBI etc. by themselves) are eligible to bid either as a sole IP or as part of a consortium.
2. Management/employees of BPCL, who intend to participate in the Proposed Transaction will be considered in accordance with the guidelines issued by DIPAM. Such employees will have to incorporate a company which only can submit the EOI, either itself as a Sole IP or as a member of a consortium. Such company must satisfy the minimum net worth criteria for a single entity and for a consortium, as the case may be. The net worth shall be assessed on the basis of practicing CA's certificate not older than 3 months from the date of invitation of EOI.
3. CPSEs and central government owned cooperative societies (i.e. where government ownership is 51% or more) are not eligible to participate in the Proposed Transaction.
4. An IP, which is required to prepare a profit & loss account, must have reported profits (profit after tax) in at least 3 (three) out of the last 5 (five) financial years. In the event that the IP is a sole bidder, and has come into existence as a result of a merger/ demerger/

⁴Excerpted from the document titled 'Preliminary Information Memorandum: For Inviting Expression of Interest For Strategic Disinvestment of Bharat Petroleum Corporation Limited (BPCL)' released by Department of Investment and Public Asset Management, Ministry of Finance, Government of India.

amalgamation of 2 or more entities, the sum of the profit after tax of such entities should be positive in 3 (three) out of the last 5 (five) financial years. In the event that the IP is a consortium or a special purpose vehicle, the lead member must have profits (after tax) in at least 3 (three) out of the last 5 (five) financial years.

Financial Criteria

For submitting the EoI and for being considered for subsequent qualification for Stage II of the Proposed Transaction, the IP shall satisfy the following financial criteria:

1. Net Worth: A minimum Net Worth of USD 10 billion (United States Dollar ten billion) as per latest audited financial statement. This Net Worth criteria may be satisfied either by the IP or by the entity into which the accounts of the IP are consolidated.

Annexure IV Rejection of EoI⁵

1. Notwithstanding anything contained in this invitation of EoI, the GoI reserves the right to reject any or all EoIs on any grounds including, the grounds of national interest, national security, public interest or any other grounds without communicating any reasons thereof and without any liability or any obligation for such rejection.
2. The GoI may also annul the EoI process and/or reject all EoIs at any time without any liability or any obligation for such acceptance, rejection or annulment, and without communicating any reasons thereof. In the event that the GoI rejects or annuls any of all the EoIs, it may, in its discretion, invite fresh EoIs hereunder.
3. The GoI reserves the right not to proceed with the EoI Process at any time, without notice or liability, and to reject any or all of the EoI without communicating any reasons.

⁵Excerpted from the document titled 'Preliminary Information Memorandum: For Inviting Expression of Interest For Strategic Disinvestment of Bharat Petroleum Corporation Limited (BPCL)' released by Department of Investment and Public Asset Management, Ministry of Finance, Government of India.

Annexure V List of Subsidiaries⁶

S.No.	Particulars	Country	% Shareholding
1.	Numaligarh Refinery Limited (NRL)	India	61.65
2.	Bharat Gas Resources Limited (BGRL)	India	100.00
3.	Bharat PetroResources Limited (BPRL)	India	100.00
4.	Bharat PetroResources JPDA Limited	India	100.00
5.	BPRL International BV	Netherlands	100.00
6.	BPRL International Singapore Pte Ltd.	Singapore	100.00
7.	BPRL Ventures BV	Netherlands	100.00
8.	BPRL Ventures Mozambique BV	Netherlands	100.00
9.	BPRL Ventures Indonesia BV	Netherlands	100.00
10.	BPRL International Ventures BV	Netherlands	100.00

⁶Excerpted from the document titled 'Preliminary Information Memorandum: For Inviting Expression of Interest For Strategic Disinvestment of Bharat Petroleum Corporation Limited (BPCL)' released by Department of Investment and Public Asset Management, Ministry of Finance, Government of India.

Annexure VI List of Joint Ventures⁷

S.No.	Particulars	Country	% Shareholding
1.	Bharat Oman Refineries Limited	India	50.00
2.	Central UP Gas Limited	India	25.00
3.	Maharashtra Natural Gas Limited	India	22.50
4.	Sabarmati Gas Limited	India	49.94
5.	Bharat Stars Services Private Limited	India	50.00
6.	Bharat Renewable Energy Limited	India	33.33
7.	Matrix Bharat Pte. Ltd.	Singapore	50.00
8.	Delhi Aviation Fuel Facility Pvt. Limited	India	37.00
9.	IBV (Brasil) Petroleo Ltda.	Brazil	50.00
10.	Mumbai Aviation Fuel Farm Facility Private Limited	India	25.00
11.	Kochi Salem Pipeline Private Limited	India	50.00
12.	BPCL-KIAL Fuel Farm Private Limited	India	74.00
13.	Haridwar Natural Gas Pvt Ltd.	India	50.00
14.	Goa Natural Gas Private Limited	India	50.00
15.	DNP Limited	India	26.00
16.	Taas India Pte Ltd.	Singapore	33.00
17.	Vankor India Pte Ltd.	Singapore	33.00
18.	Falcon Oil & Gas BV	Netherlands	30.00
19.	Ratnagiri Refinery & Petrochemicals Ltd.	India	25.00
20.	LLC TYNGD	Russia	9.87
21.	Urja Bharat Pte. Ltd.	Singapore	50.00
22.	Assam Bio Refinery (P) Ltd.	India	50.00
23.	Indradhanush Gas Grid Ltd.	India	20.00

⁷Excerpted from the document titled 'Preliminary Information Memorandum: For Inviting Expression of Interest For Strategic Disinvestment of Bharat Petroleum Corporation Limited (BPCL)' released by Department of Investment and Public Asset Management, Ministry of Finance, Government of India.

Annexure VII List of Associates⁸

S.No.	Particulars	Country	% Shareholding
1.	Indraprastha Gas Limited	India	22.50
2.	Petronet LNG Limited	India	12.50
3.	GSPL India Gasnet Limited	India	11.00
4.	GSPL India Transco Limited	India	11.00
5.	Kannur International Airport Limited	India	21.68
6.	Petroleum India International	India	18.18
7.	Petronet India Limited	India	16.00
8.	Petronet CI Limited	India	11.00
9.	FINO Paytech Limited	India	20.73
10.	Brahmaputra Cracker and Polymer & Limited	India	10.00
11.	Mozambique LNG 1 Pte Ltd	Singapore	10.00
12.	JSC Vankorneft	Russia	7.89

⁸Excerpted from the document titled 'Preliminary Information Memorandum: For Inviting Expression of Interest For Strategic Disinvestment of Bharat Petroleum Corporation Limited (BPCL)' released by Department of Investment and Public Asset Management, Ministry of Finance, Government of India.

Annexure VIII Union Budget 2020-21

Particulars	Amount (in ₹Crore)
1. Revenue Receipts	2020926
2. Tax Revenue (Net to Centre)	1635909
3. Non Tax Revenue	385017
4. Capital Receipts	1021304
5. Recovery of Loans	14967
6. Other Receipts	210000
7. Borrowings and Other Liabilities	796337
8. Total Receipts (1+4)	3042230
9. Total Expenditure (10+13)	3042230
10. On Revenue Account	2630145
11. Interest Payments	708203
12. Grants in Aid for creation of capital assets	206500
13. On Capital Account	412085
14. Revenue Deficit (10-1)	609219
15. Effective Revenue Deficit (14-12)	402719
16. Fiscal Deficit (14-12) [9-(1+5+6)]	796337
17. Primary Deficit (16-11)	88134

Notes:

1. GDP for BE 2020-2021 has been projected at ₹22489420 Crore assuming 10.0 % growth over the estimated GDP of ₹20442233 Crore for 2019-2020 (RE).
2. Individual items in this document may not sum up to the totals due to rounding off.

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